

Visualisation of large Labelled Transition Systems

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Abstract

A formal model describes the behaviour of a program, protocol or other system. The properties of this model can be verified, such that we can prove these properties with absolute certainty.

Visualising the state space of a formal model is an important tool for their development. This thesis focuses on visualising such a state space as a graph.

We present a layout technique that provides efficient graph layouts for graphs with over 10 000 nodes, discuss the effectiveness of different edge shapes, and present multiple ways of highlighting the structure of the graph. We present a rendering procedure capable of rendering graphs larger than 10 000 nodes while supporting these techniques. We implemented these techniques in a tool and use it to measure the performance of the techniques. The effectiveness of these techniques is analysed using a survey on the tool in a few practical applications.

We conclude that these techniques *can* effectively be used in one visualisation to assist in formal model development.

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1 Introduction

Software is often tested for unwanted behaviour. However, regular testing can't provide a definite proof that a program does not contain unwanted behaviour. To be certain about the behaviour of the software, one can write the program as a formal model.

Many systems, like protocols, software systems and circuit networks can be written in a formal language like a Process Equation. These models can be automatically checked on properties that are expressed in a state-oriented mathematical language.

Development of these models is usually assisted with a visualisation of all possible execution paths, represented as a Labelled Transition System (LTS). These visualisations give insight on the situation causing the unwanted behaviour, so the designer can quickly find the fault in the model.

When developing a formal model, designers are often faced with difficulties in visualising the state space of the model. Just visualising the graph itself is insufficient when the graph is large. The structure of the graph becomes harder to understand, and a good layout becomes harder to compute for graphs of over 1 000 nodes.

There are generic visualisers that lack the tools and visualisation techniques that support model checking. Visualisers that are designed for model checking are not efficient enough to visualise large graphs.

We will research techniques and strategies to visualise large and complex graphs, and provide functionality that is specific for the development of LTS graphs. This is achieved by combining existing visualisation techniques and providing additional visualisation for LTS specific properties.

As preparation on this study, we performed an exploratory study to see what the existing visualisation options are, and how effective these options are. This study discussed a number of visualisation techniques and their application on LTS graphs. It also performed a survey to obtain predictions on the effectiveness of these techniques. This survey presented the techniques to 16 experienced users of LTSGraph, which is an existing visualisation tool in the formal model development toolkit mCRL2 [4]. The study concluded with a rating for each technique on their perceived effectiveness.

In this thesis, we research the techniques that were the highest rated techniques in the survey. We also included some techniques in our research that were not included in the exploratory study.

In chapter 2, we discuss some of the techniques that we researched in our exploratory study, which looks at alternative ways of visualising LTS graphs. Chapter 3 explains the technical terms used in this thesis, and chapter 4 describes the problem that we are planning to solve. The use cases of this problem are analysed in chapter 5 before we look at the techniques.

The graph layout is discussed in chapter 6, and considers one fast technique and one quality technique. We show that these can be combined, and measure the improvements. Graphic techniques are discussed in chapter 7, where we look at different edge shapes, and how to show the graph structure using colors. For complexity reduction techniques we look at different clustering techniques, and other ways of reducing the size of the graph in chapter 8. Additionally, we describe a rendering procedure in chapter 9 that supports these techniques efficiently for graphs with over 10 000 nodes.

These visualisation techniques are tested in a survey, which will be discussed in chapter 10. We briefly consider the threats to validity in chapter 11. In chapter 12 we draw our conclusions

on the effectiveness of each technique, where we combine the performance results with the survey results to answer the hypotheses that we constructed for each of the techniques.

We look at opportunities to extend on this in chapter 13.

One of the use cases we studied was graph comparison. We studied multiple algorithms and designed case-specific optimisations, but eventually we concluded that graph comparison was not feasible on the scale that we wanted to support. We will mention our findings on graph comparison algorithms in section 13.1.

2 Previous Work

Graph visualisation is a widely discussed topic, with many practical applications. Each application has different requirements for the visualisation, and there is not one optimal solution. We will restrict to visualisations of the state space of a model, which model discrete behaviour. Our report focuses on visualising these state spaces as Labelled Transition Systems (LTS), which are directed graphs with edge labels.

While state spaces are usually expressed as LTS graphs, there are other methods of representing these. In this section, we will discuss some alternative representations that have been proposed to analyse state spaces.

2.1 Rank clustered graph

A study of Groote and Ham [8] describes a state cluster visualisation that visualizes states in discs based on a rank, creating a shape that largely resembles the structure of the graph, as seen in Figure 1. This is capable of visualising state spaces with over 1 000 000 nodes, but does not visualize individual nodes.

This technique uses a simplified tree representation as a basis for the structure of the graph. Each node is given a rank number, and clustered with nodes that share both the rank and the path to the root. Each cluster is represented as a disc, creating a 3D tree model that is displayed. Modifications on this algorithm are proposed by Ploeger and Tankink [11] to ensure an optimal layout of this tree structure. Additional coloring is added to draw attention to certain attributes and branching properties.

This visualisation is implemented in a tool, and distributed as part of the mCRL2 toolkit [4]. The tool is effective in efficiently visualising very large graphs, while allowing viewing individual nodes on demand. This helps to understand how the behaviour of the system branches, and how a possible symmetry is reflected in the graph. However, it also introduces jumps where a high-rank node connects to a lower-rank node. These jumps may make it difficult to see the complete structure of the graph. Graphs with many edges also create large clusters, which is harder to visualise with this method.

2.2 Attribute-based clustering

A study of Pretorius and van Wijk [12] describes an exploration method for clustering graphs based on a subset of the node attributes. This is visualized in a tree-structure, where each layer creates a further distinction between attributes. The transitions of the full state space are combined and visualized in the leaf layer of the tree as an arc diagram. An image of this visualisation is given in Figure 2

This representation is very effective to get insight on the possible changes a system can have, and to identify behavioral patterns and symmetries of the transitions. It does however

Figure 1: A rank clustered graph, created using LTSView

Figure 2: A representation of a graph using Attribute-based clustering, created using Diagraphica

(a) A graph visualised in MatLink, taken from [10] (b) A graph with paths superimposed, taken from [14]

Figure 3: Adjacency matrix visualisations

not give a clear overview where these transitions may happen, nor does it show other details about the graph.

This visualisation is also implemented in a tool, and distributed as part of the mCRL2 toolkit [4].

2.3 Adjacency Matrices

Instead of a spatial representation of a graph, we can also encode the connections in matrices as argued by Keller, Eckert and Clarkson [13]. The matrix rows and columns both enumerate all states, and the matrix elements represent the transitions. A transition from state a to b is then encoded by coloring the element of row a , column b . This representation works well with small, highly connected graphs. The spreading of the information also makes it hard to follow paths, which is an important task in our use case.

To increase the performance of path tracing, some researchers have proposed methods to visualize the transitions of a state when it is selected. The MatLink approach of Henry and Fekete [10] can be seen in Figure 3a, and shows the arcs on the sides of the matrix. The approach of Shen and Ma [14] shows the paths inside the matrix itself, and can be seen in Figure 3b.

These representations are effective for analysing detail interactions in graphs with a very high number of connections. It is easy to find all connections of a single node, and how many connections each node have. However, even with the path visualisations, path tracing remains difficult. To find the path between two distant nodes, one would need additional tools to visualise them.

3 Technical background

We will explain a number of technical terms related to model checking, graph representations and computer visualisation. We give definitions of graph representations, equivalence relations and other graph-related properties.

3.1 Formal models

The term formal model refers to any specification of a system without informal elements. This is the case when the model specification is entirely mathematically defined. A visualisation of the state space is helpful for analysing these models, and this is the main use case of our research.

Formal models are used to create a software design that satisfies the requirements. Most development tools therefore include functionality to formalise requirements, and test whether the model adheres to them. Software can be derived from the formal models by using it as an informal structure description. Some languages allow a conversion program to convert the formal specification directly into software.

We will assume that the systems that we model are capable of executing atomic *actions*. These actions are chosen non-deterministic from all possible actions of the system in its given state. The set of actions is static and known.

3.2 Graphs

A graph is a node-link diagram, consisting of nodes connected by edges. Graphs model pairwise relationships between objects, either directional or undirected. They are used to model a multitude of systems, and are widely used in among others, physics, linguistics and computer science. There are many variations of graphs, which differ in the additional information of nodes and edges, and whether edges are directional or not. We will first consider an unlabelled directed graph.

Definition 1 (Graph) *An unlabelled, directed graph is defined as: $G = \langle S, T \rangle$ with*

- S is a set of nodes
- $T \subseteq S \times S$ is a set of edges between the nodes

If there exists an edge $(s_1, s_2) \in T$, we denote this edge with $s_1 \rightarrow s_2$. For a graph $G = \langle S, T \rangle$, two nodes $s_1, s_2 \in S$ are considered *adjacent* and *connected* if there exists an edge $(s_1, s_2) \in T$.

A subgraph is a subset of the states and edges from an other graph.

Definition 2 (Subgraph) *A graph $F = \langle S', T' \rangle$ is a subgraph of $G = \langle S, T \rangle$ denoted as $F \subseteq G$ if*

- $S' \subseteq S$
- $T' = T \cap (S' \times S')$

By following edges in the graph, one can create a path. Paths are a series of nodes connected by edges, and can occur in both directed and undirected graphs.

Definition 3 (Path) *For a graph $G = \langle S, T \rangle$, a path starting at a node $s \in S$ is a series of nodes $p = s_0, s_1, \dots, s_i$, where for each subsequent pair of nodes there exists an edge $\langle s_i, s_{i+1} \rangle \in T$ in G .*

An Infinite path

A maximal path

Using the definition of paths, we can also define unreachable and unavoidable nodes.

Definition 4 (Unavoidable) For a directed graph $G = \langle S, T \rangle$, a set of nodes $M \subseteq S$ is unavoidable from a node $s \in S$, if all maximal paths starting at s contain a state in M .

Definition 5 (Unreachable) For a directed graph $G = \langle S, T \rangle$, a set of nodes $M \subseteq S$ is unreachable if no path exists from s to any state in M .

3.3 Transition systems and LTS

A transition system is a graph that models the behaviour of some system. The nodes of such system represent the different states of the system, and a given behaviour can be seen as a path through the graph. From any given node, the future behaviour of the system is independent from how the node is reached.

There are multiple types of transition systems, and we will focus on Labelled Transition Systems (LTS). An LTS is a type of graph that models how the state of a system changes based on the actions executed. In an LTS, each transition has a label, indicating either an external signal that causes the transition, or actions resulting from the transition.

Definition 6 (LTS) A Labelled Transition System (LTS) is defined as a tuple $A = \langle S, T, L, s_{initial} \rangle$:

- S is a set of states
- T is a labelled transition relation $T \subseteq S \times L \times S$
- L is a set of labels
- $s_{initial} \in S$ is the initial state

We may leave the initial state $s_{initial}$ implicit when we consider an LTS.

A transition between states $s_1, s_2 \in S$ with label a will be written as $s_1 \xrightarrow{a} s_2$. We assume there can be a special action $\tau \in L$ that represents an internal action. We write $s_1 \xrightarrow{\bar{a}} s_2$ if either $s_1 \xrightarrow{a} s_2$ or $s_1 = s_2 \wedge a = \tau$

Example LTS Figure 4 shows an example of an LTS. This LTS models a coffee machine that dispenses coffee or tea.

The machine starts in the uppermost state. When a coin is inserted, as indicated by the label *coin*, the system transitions to the next state. In this state, it no longer accepts a coin, but instead accepts one of two actions: *coffee* or *tea*. Executing any of these actions, probably by pressing a button, will eventually cause the system to trigger *dispensing*: an action executed by the system. Transitions are considered instantaneous, so the system will wait for a *reset* action while dispensing the drink. States without any outgoing transitions are referred to as *deadlocked* states. When an LTS enters a deadlocked state, no further action is possible.

A sequence of actions in an LTS is known as a *trace*. A single trace describes a sequence of actions executed by the system.

Definition 7 (Trace) Let $A = \langle S, T, L \rangle$ be a labelled transition system. A trace in A is a sequence of actions $a_0 \dots a_n$, such that there exists a path $p = s_0 \dots s_{n+1}$ for which holds that $\forall_i 0 \leq i \leq n \mid s_i \xrightarrow{a_i} s_{i+1}$.

Given a state s , we define $Tr(s)$ to be the set of all traces $t = a_0 \dots a_i$ in A starting in s .

Figure 4: A LTS of a coffee machine

An LTS is considered *deterministic* if for every state, there are no two outgoing edges with the same label.

Definition 8 (Deterministic) Let $A = \langle S, T, L \rangle$ be a labelled transition system. A is considered deterministic if for any given action $a \in L$, for every two transitions $s_1 \xrightarrow{a} s_2$ and $s_1 \xrightarrow{a} s_3$, it holds that $s_2 = s_3$.

Two states are considered *confluent* if the external behaviours starting from these states are indistinguishable [7].

Definition 9 (Confluence) Let $A = \langle S, T, L \rangle$ be a labelled transition system, and let $W \subseteq T$ be a set of τ transitions in A . A is considered W -confluent iff for each transition $s_0 \xrightarrow{\tau} s_1$ in W and for all $s_0 \xrightarrow{a} s_2$, there exists a state $s_3 \in S$ such that $s_1 \xrightarrow{\bar{a}} s_3$ and $s_2 \xrightarrow{\bar{a}} s_3$. We call A confluent if A is W' -confluent, where W' is the set of all τ transitions in A .

Definition 10 (Node confluence) Let $A = \langle S, T, L \rangle$ be a transition system and let $s_0, s_1 \in S$ be two states in A . We call s_0 and s_1 confluent, iff there exists a set W such that A is W -confluent and $s_0 \xrightarrow{\tau} s_1 \in W$.

Note that $W \subseteq T$, and hence for confluent states $s_0, s_1 \in S$, it holds that $s_0 \xrightarrow{\tau} s_1 \in T$.

Different LTS graphs may describe the same behaviour, accept the same traces or have other similarities. For these situations, we define equivalence classes that indicate a similarity between graphs [6].

Definition 11 (Isomorphism) Let there be two LTS graphs $A = \langle S, T, L \rangle$ and $B = \langle S', T', L' \rangle$. An isomorphism between A and B is a bijection $f : S \rightarrow S'$ such that for every edge $s_0 \xrightarrow{a} s_1 \in T$ in A , there exists an edge $f(s_0) \xrightarrow{a} f(s_1) \in T'$ in B . A and B are considered isomorphic if there exists an isomorphism between A and B .

Definition 12 (Trace equivalence) Let there be two LTS graphs $A = \langle S, T, L, s_{initial} \rangle$ and $B = \langle S', T', L', s'_{initial} \rangle$. Two states $s_0, s_1 \in S$ are trace equivalent if $Tr(s_0) = Tr(s_1)$. A and B are trace equivalent if $Tr(s_{initial}) = Tr(s'_{initial})$.

Definition 13 (Simulation) Let there be two LTS graphs $A = \langle S, T, L \rangle$ and $B = \langle S', T', L' \rangle$. A simulation is a relation $R \subseteq S \times S'$ such that if $(s_1, s'_1) \in R$, then for every $s_1 \xrightarrow{a} s_2$ there is a transition $s'_1 \xrightarrow{a} s'_2$ and $(s_2, s'_2) \in R$.

We say that state s_0 is *simulated* by state s_1 if there exists a simulation R such that $(s_0, s_1) \in R$. If the inverse of R is also a simulation, then we call R a *bisimulation*.

Definition 14 (Bisimulation) A bisimulation is a relation R on two graphs such that if $(s_1, s'_1) \in R$ then for every $s_1 \xrightarrow{a} s_2$ there is a transition $s'_1 \xrightarrow{a} s'_2$, and for every $s'_1 \xrightarrow{a} s'_2$ there is a transition $s_1 \xrightarrow{a} s_2$, and $(s_2, s'_2) \in R$. Two graphs $A = \langle S, T, L, s_{initial} \rangle$ and $B = \langle S', T', L', s'_{initial} \rangle$ are said to be bisimilar if there is a bisimulation R for which holds that $(s_{initial}, s'_{initial}) \in R$.

A bisimulation between two graphs indicates that if one graph can execute some action a after a given trace t , then the other graph can also execute action a after the same trace t . This is different from trace equivalence in the choices you have while following a trace. There may be two different paths with the same trace, where you have different options at the end of the traces. Branching bisimulation allows multiple τ transitions to interleave the bisimilarity condition.

Definition 15 (Branching Bisimulation) Let there be two LTS graphs $A = \langle S, T, L \rangle$ and $B = \langle S', T', L' \rangle$, states $s_1, s_2 \in S$ and $s'_1 \in S'$. A relation $R \subseteq S \times S'$ is called a branching simulation when, if $(s_1, s'_1) \in R$ and $s_1 \xrightarrow{a} s_2$, then either $a = \tau$ and $(s_2, s'_1) \in R$, or there exists states $s'_2, s'_3 \in S'$ such that $s'_1 \xrightarrow{\tau} \dots \xrightarrow{\tau} s'_2 \xrightarrow{a} s'_3$, $(s_1, s'_2) \in R$ and $(s_2, s'_3) \in R$.

If the converse $R^T \subseteq S' \times S$ is also a branching simulation, then this is a branching bisimulation

Two graphs $A = \langle S, T, L, s_{initial} \rangle$ and $B = \langle S', T', L', s'_{initial} \rangle$ are said to be branching bisimilar if there is a branching bisimulation R for which it holds that $(s_{initial}, s'_{initial}) \in R$.

4 Problem description

Every formal model has a state space, which describes every behaviour it can express. Visualising this state space can help the development or improvement of the model. This is further improved using techniques to draw attention to patterns and important properties.

The effectiveness of the state space visualisation depends heavily on the visualisation techniques used. Existing graph visualisations are often insufficient for industrial use cases. Some specifications used in industrial applications have state spaces of over 100 000 states, which puts demands on both performance and visual complexity. Even when reducing graphs using branching bisimulation and other complexity reduction techniques, there often remain graphs of thousands of states.

There exists a tool in the mCRL2 toolkit [4] to visualize LTS graphs, but this tool is only sufficient to visualize small graphs with less than 100 nodes. Other tools summarize the structure of the graph, showing generalized information about specific transitions or only considers a specific trace through the graph. To visualize large state spaces, we have to consider what information we have to show, and how to show this without reducing oversight.

The goal of this research is to analyse which visualisation techniques support the analysis of state spaces and the development of formal models. We perform this analysis by answering the following research questions:

- **What are the use-cases for a state space visualisation**
- **Which existing visualisation techniques are effective for these use cases**
- **Can we effectively combine visualisation techniques for LTS graphs**

The first question will be answered in section 5, the second will be discussed in sections 6 to 8. For the third question we look at the performance aspect in section 9, and the effectiveness in section 10 using a survey.

4.1 Methodology

We first research the use cases of state space visualisations. These use cases will be constructed in an interview with an expert in formal model checking. We specifically look at use cases where a visualisation of the state space aids the development of the model.

We then research a number of existing graph visualisation techniques, and analyse how they support state space visualisation. We discuss for each technique how it may affect other techniques, and if necessary we discuss how the technique can be modified to combine with other techniques. We conclude each technique with a testable hypothesis that argues its effectiveness.

The effectiveness of the techniques will be tested by implementing them in a tool. This tool will be used to perform a survey to test the hypotheses of the techniques. In this survey we have the user perform a series of assignments that reflect regular analysis work. Using the results, we will verify or refute each of the constructed hypotheses.

4.2 Considerations for graph representation

There are many alternatives to representing the state space as an LTS graph. We discussed some of them in section 2. While these visualisations are generally effective, there is still a demand for a node-link representation of the state space.

We expect that it is important that a visualisation allows you to trace specific execution paths. In addition, we expect that analysing the behaviour of the system starting from a specific node also helps understanding a state space. Our preliminary research indicated that an LTS representation is the most effective visualisation that supports these situations. Additionally, the intuitive meaning of an LTS representation helps for a quick understanding of the system behaviour.

4.3 Considerations for tool development

As part of our thesis, we implement the techniques that we will discuss in a tool. Initially, we planned on extending the LTSGraph tool in the mCRL2 toolkit, but doing so would mean that we had to adhere to the existing implementation of the graph structure. As we expanded LTSGraph, we also created a prototype of each element separately in a mock-up program. It would show that development on the prototype was far more efficient.

We decided to stop development on LTSGraph, and create a new program based on the prototype. This allowed us to redesign the basic node structure, and gives us more freedom in what elements to implement. This also meant that we could implement the efficient rendering procedure for drawing large graphs.

Doing so would however also prevent us from using predicate manipulation, state space analysis and other mCRL2 built-in features. We decided that this was a minor issue, and could be worked around.

5 Visualisation use cases

In this section we consider the use cases of our visualisation. We talked with a researcher in formal models about the procedures of constructing a formal model, and where a visualisation of the state space could be useful. From this discussion, we constructed a number of use cases that are relevant to a visualisation. We will describe a number of scenarios that we consider particularly relevant, and we will refer to these scenarios when discussing the techniques.

5.1 Model Development

During development, a visualisation of the state space can be used to recognize certain behaviours of the model. For example, if the system works in different phases, the visualisation can be used to see how the model steps from one phase to another. Deadlocked states indicate design errors, and should be resolved early in the design process.

Even without testing formal properties, the state space visualisation can be used to identify errors in the model. For example, asynchronous elements and symmetric behaviour result in distinct patterns in the state space. If these are expected but not visible, then this may indicate an error in the model.

Use Case 1 (Deadlock) *As the model is being developed, a visualisation of the state space should allow for a quick evaluation of deadlocks in the system. These deadlocks can be indicators of simple errors in the model.*

Scenario A controller is built for a system that repeatedly processes items with three independent elements. When visualising the first iteration of the model, the engineers conclude that all execution paths result in deadlocks. Researching the edges entering the deadlocked states gives an indication of when the system deadlocks.

Use Case 2 (Asynchronous sections) *Asynchronous sections and independent behaviour should be easy to recognize. This allows for superficial confirmation whether the model follows the intended behaviour.*

Scenario The controller of the previous example is improved, and now shows a 2-dimensional grid in a loop. Three independent elements should result in a 3-dimensional grid, and the engineers conclude that some of the sections are not independent in the current model.

5.2 Property verification

Once a set of formal properties have been constructed, the visualisation is used to determine why properties do not hold. The verification tools may generate counterexamples for properties that do not hold. These counterexamples are subgraphs of the state space, and can be visualized.

As the properties reason in terms of actions, it is important to visualise the action labels effectively. When there are specific undesired states, it should be clear what sequence of actions lead to these states.

Use Case 3 (Visualising counterexample) *Highlighting the edges of a counterexample in the original graph shows how the counterexample relates to the rest of the state space. Understanding what behaviour does not lead to the counterexample should help to understand why a property fails.*

Scenario A model checking tool tries to verify a mutual exclusion property on a model for some new protocol. The model checker returns negative, and generates a subgraph as counterexample. The engineer visualises this subgraph together with the original graph to see what sections of the state space allow this behaviour.

Use Case 4 (Property visualisation) *Some counterexamples cover the entire state space. Visualising where the separate parts of a property holds in the state space should give more insight in why the property fails.*

Scenario An engineer analyses the property that a specific action cannot be repeated, but the property fails. The counterexample is large, so instead the engineer uses property visualisation. The visualiser highlights the states where the given action is possible and repeatable. This shows the engineer exactly the problematic states, which were not visible in the counterexample.

5.3 Change analysis

Models evolve during development, and may change as results of a changing environment. It is informative to understand how the state space changes as a result of these modifications. Situations may occur where a property holds in one iteration, and not in the next. Knowing the differences helps to quickly understand the cause of this.

Use Case 5 (Graph comparison) *Improving or optimising a model may change the behaviour of the system. The visualisation should be able to highlight these changes and allow a comparison between the old and new model.*

Scenario An engineer recently finished a model where all properties hold. He applies an optimisation, and finds that some properties now fail. Rather than analysing each property one-by-one, he instead visualises the difference between the two graphs. This shows him exactly what portions of the state space have changed, allowing him to focus on just those sections.

5.4 Focus graphs

We want to visualise arbitrary state spaces with up to 50 000 elements. To show examples of our techniques and to compare visualisation effectiveness between different types of graphs, we selected a number of LTS graphs which we will use to show our techniques on. These graphs are shown in Figure 5. The images are generated using the final iteration of our tool, and show the graphs as node-link diagrams.

These graphs are chosen to cover a wide variety of structural properties. Each of them is generated from an existing formal model, and most of them have been used for analysis.

Alma (5a) is a large graph, with a straightforward structure. This graph serves as a representation of an average graph.

Bakery (5b) is a graph where many nodes are connected to the initial state. This state space is hard to visualise as an LTS, and helps to show the limitations of the techniques.

Leader (5c) is generated from multiple independent, acyclic processes, and has a large degree of asynchrony. This graph shows how the techniques visualise asynchronous sections, when the number of independent processes is large.

Lift (5d) is a large graph composed of three symmetric sections. This graph is hard to show in one piece, and has multiple levels of symmetry.

Minepump (5e) is a small graph that contains an external signal, which has a delayed handling. This graph could benefit well from complexity reduction.

Twilight (5f) is a graph with simple asynchronous sections. This graph is mostly used as a simple example.

These graphs will be the focus of our research, and we evaluate the effectiveness of our techniques on these graphs. We do not intend to make every visualisation effective on every graph. We will use these graphs in our final evaluation survey as well.

(a) alma

(b) bakery

(c) leader

(d) lift

(e) minepump

(f) twilight

Figure 5: Focus graphs of the study

6 Layout

With the use cases of section 5, we analysed various existing visualisation techniques, and analysed how we can apply these techniques for visualising state spaces as LTS graphs.

First we introduce a number of properties that improve the readability of a layout. We discuss the advantages of 3-dimensional visualisation over other methods. We then look at algorithms that generate a graph layout. These algorithms determine the position of the nodes and edges in a graph to make a readable layout.

Layout algorithms can be divided in two categories, iterative and static. An iterative layout improves the layout in iterations, until an acceptable layout is reached, while a static layout generates the layout in one computation. We present one technique for each category, followed by an analysis on the combination of the two techniques.

Lastly we draw a conclusion on the effectiveness of the combined layout technique.

6.1 Ideal layout properties

There are a number of layout characteristics that improve the readability of a layout. We will give some major properties that we consider important here.

These properties are specifically chosen to support following traces and detect the graph structures. They should be effective for any type of graph.

- It is important that connected nodes are reasonably close together. A trace is easier to follow if the edges are short and do not overlap other edges. Short edges also reduce the number of crossing edges when projecting in 2 dimensions, reducing the visual clutter.
- In contrast, unconnected nodes should be distanced from each other. We must prevent unconnected subsections of the graph from overlapping.
- Asynchronous sections should be easily recognizable. This can be achieved by ensuring that these structures form clear grids or cubic grids.
- Symmetric parts of the graph should be graphically symmetric as well. If one part of a symmetry is presented in one way, the other part of the symmetry should be presented in a similar or mirrored way.
- In addition, state space representations have a tendency to generate substructures with high connectivity between nodes. There should be distance between these structures to recognize different sections of the graph behaviour.

6.2 Graph projection

Graphs are usually displayed on a 2-dimensional plane, as shown in Figure 6a. This representation gives a clear overview for small and simple graphs, but can quickly become hard to read for large graphs, or graphs with a high connectivity. LTS graphs of state spaces usually have highly connected sections, and especially asynchronous sections become hard to read in a 2-dimensional representation. An example from the *twilight* graph is seen in Figure 7a.

A 3-dimensional visualisation allows the user to change its perspective on the graph, to allow the user to make a 3-dimensional mental image of the graph. An example is shown in Figure 6b. This perspective change is in general implemented as a camera rotating around a pivot.

Figure 6: An arbitrary section of the *minepump* graph in 2D and in 3D

Figure 7: An asynchronous section of the *twilight* graph in 2D and 3D

A 3-dimensional perspective does however require interaction to be effective. Without rotation, it becomes difficult to tell graph sections apart. This makes the visualisation less effective when used as static media like figures.

If the LTS contains multiple asynchronous processes, then the state space is likely to contain multiple sequences of actions interleaving each other. In these situations, a higher dimensional representation allows for a better visualisation of these structures. With the correct perspective, one can find sections more easily, as seen in Figure 7b.

We also considered the possibilities of using a 4-dimensional visualisation. This could be implemented as giving all nodes a 4-dimensional coordinate, and projecting these coordinates to 3 dimensions before rendering the graph. However, using such a system would be very hard to understand, and may increase the difficulty of understanding the graph rather than reducing it. For this reason we decided to focus on a 3-dimensional positioning of nodes.

6.3 Force-based layout algorithm

As we mentioned in section 6.1, we should move connected states closer together and states that are not connected away from each other. This improvement can be achieved by modelling the graph as a forces simulation. This specific algorithm has been specialized to work for LTS

graphs in particular.

A force directed layout models each node as a charged particle, repelling other nodes, and each transition as a spring, attracting connected nodes. Simulating this system for long enough causes the graph to relax to a local stable equilibrium. This is calculated in discrete steps, and is therefore an approximation. We don't require the computation to be accurate, as we are only interested in the equilibrium position. Because of this, we should choose the step size that converges to its equilibrium the quickest.

We studied the algorithm implemented in LTSGraph, a tool in the mCRL2 toolkit. We applied modifications in the `NodeRepulsion` and `EdgeAttraction` functions to handle some edge cases. When nodes are very close together, their repulsion on each other is very large, and the simulation becomes less accurate. To circumvent this, we limited the maximum net force that can be exerted on a node. This does not change the equilibrium layout, as in an equilibrium, the net forces are zero.

The resulting implementation of this layout algorithm is described in algorithm 1. The pseudocode uses `Vector3` to indicate a mathematical 3-dimensional vector, written as $(\mathbb{R}, \mathbb{R}, \mathbb{R})$. It also assumes a function `OUTGOINGEDGESOF(n)` that maps each node n to all edges $n \xrightarrow{l} m$ starting in n . This function can be precomputed for every node in the graph, and reused every iteration.

The algorithm accepts a graph $\langle N, E \rangle$, and `deltaTime` as the time since the last iteration. The algorithm uses parameters `NATURAL_LENGTH`, `REPULSION`, `ATTRACTION`, `EDGE_REPULSION` and σ . These will be discussed below. We assume edges store their source and destination in the fields `from` and `to`, and have a `handle` field that stores a position in the middle of the edge, determining the edge curvature.

The algorithm consists of three parts.

1: Node repulsion computes the repelling force between nodes. The force between each pair of nodes (a, b) is computed once, applied to a and the reverse is applied to b . The force vector is computed using algorithm 2: `NODEREPULSION(a, b, natLength, repulsion)`.

2: Edge attraction computes the attraction between nodes caused by edges. Similar as for node repulsion, the force between the nodes of an edge $a \xrightarrow{l} b$ is computed once, applied to a and the reverse is applied to b . The force vector is computed using algorithm 3 `EDGEATTRACTION(a, b, natLength, attraction)`.

3: Edge handle computes the forces between edge handles, causing edges to bend. This makes any two edges that connect the same nodes to become separate. In addition, edges that share a node will be more evenly spaced out. Every handle is attracted by both nodes it is connected to, forcing it to the middle of the two nodes. This attraction is computed using algorithm `EDGEATTRACTION(a, b, natLength, attraction)`. Additionally, it repulses other node handles using `NODEREPULSION(a, b, natLength, repulsion)`. This repulsion is only computed between edges that share at least one node to reduce computational complexity.

The parameters `NATURAL_LENGTH`, `REPULSION`, `ATTRACTION` and `EDGE_REPULSION` together control the exact shape of the layout.

- `NATURAL_LENGTH` controls the distance between nodes, and has minimal effect on the general structure.

Algorithm 1 Force directed layout

```
1: procedure FORCE DIRECTED LAYOUT( $N, E, \text{deltaTime}$ )
2:    $nForces \leftarrow \text{Map}(\text{Node} \rightarrow \text{Vector3})$ 
3:   for all unique pairs  $(m, n)$  in  $N \times N$  do ▷ part 1
4:      $force \leftarrow \text{NODEREPULSION}(n, m, \text{NATURAL\_LENGTH}, \text{REPULSION})$ 
5:      $nForces[n] \leftarrow nForces[n] + force$ 
6:      $nForces[m] \leftarrow nForces[m] - force$ 
7:   for all edges  $(a, b)$  in  $E$  do ▷ part 2
8:      $force \leftarrow \text{EDGEATTRACTION}(a, b, \text{NATURAL\_LENGTH}, \text{ATTRACTION})$ 
9:      $nForces[a] \leftarrow nForces[a] + force$ 
10:     $nForces[b] \leftarrow nForces[b] - force$ 
11:  for all nodes  $n$  in  $N$  do
12:    Add  $nForces[n] * \text{deltaTime}$  to the position of  $n$ 
13:   $eForces \leftarrow \text{Map}(\text{EdgeHandle} \rightarrow \text{Vector3})$ 
14:  for all nodes  $n$  in  $N$  do ▷ part 3
15:     $E_n \leftarrow \text{OUTGOINGEDGESOF}(n)$ 
16:    for all unique pairs  $(a, b)$  in  $E_n \times E_n$  do
17:       $force \leftarrow \text{NODEREPULSION}(a.\text{handle}, b.\text{handle}, \text{NATURAL\_LENGTH}, \text{EDGE\_REPULSION})$ 
18:       $eForces[a] \leftarrow eForces[a] + force$ 
19:       $eForces[b] \leftarrow eForces[b] - force$ 
20:  for all edge  $e$  in  $E$  do
21:    if  $e.\text{from} = e.\text{to}$  then
22:       $force \leftarrow \text{EDGEATTRACTION}(e.\text{handle}, e.\text{from}, \text{NATURAL\_LENGTH}, \text{ATTRACTION})$ 
23:    else
24:       $dist \leftarrow \frac{\text{distance}(e.\text{from}, e.\text{to})}{\sigma}$ 
25:       $force \leftarrow \text{EDGEATTRACTION}(e.\text{handle}, e.\text{from}, dist, 1)$ 
26:       $force \leftarrow force + \text{EDGEATTRACTION}(e.\text{handle}, e.\text{to}, dist, 1)$ 
27:       $eForces[e] = eForces[e] + force$ 
28:  for all edge  $e$  in  $E$  do
29:    Move  $e.\text{handle}$  by  $eForces[e] * \text{deltaTime}$ 
```

- **REPULSION** controls the effect of nodes repelling each other. In contrary to **NATURAL_LENGTH**, this does not affect edge forces.
- **ATTRACTION** controls the effect of edges. When both **REPULSION** and **ATTRACTION** are raised equally, the effect is similar to an increase in step size.
- **EDGE_REPUSLION** controls the effect of edge handles repelling each other. This has no influence on node positions.
- σ is a small number used to limit the repulsion forces on nodes. It should be chosen large enough that it prevents extreme node movement, but far smaller than the average node distance.

Barnes-Hut heuristic Force directed algorithm 1 contains a quadratic component to calculate the repulsion between all pairs of nodes. To improve the running time of this section of the algorithm, we considered using the Barnes-Hut n-body algorithm as described by J. Barnes and P. Hut [3] to compute these repulsion forces.

Algorithm 2 Node repulsion computation

```
1: procedure NODEREPULSION(Vector3  $a$ , Vector3  $b$ , natLength, repulsion)
2:    $aToB \leftarrow b - a$ 
3:   if  $length(aToB) < \sigma$  then
4:     return random vector
5:   else
6:      $lengthFraction \leftarrow \max(\frac{length(aToB)}{2}, \frac{natLength}{10})$ 
7:      $r \leftarrow \frac{repulsion}{lengthFraction^3}$ 
8:     return  $aToB * r$ 
```

Algorithm 3 Edge attraction computation

```
1: procedure EDGEATTRACTION(Vector3  $a$ , Vector3  $b$ , natLength, attraction)
2:    $aToB \leftarrow b - a$ 
3:    $dist \leftarrow \max(length(aToB), 1)$ 
4:    $factor \leftarrow attraction * 100 * \log(\frac{dist}{natLength+1}) / dist$ 
5:   return  $aToB * factor$ 
```

The Barnes-Hut algorithm is a heuristic for computing forces exerted between a large number of objects. For each object, the computation towards distant objects is approximated by computing the effect of the center of mass of these objects combined. We can use this algorithm to approximate the repulsion between nodes with little loss of accuracy.

Setting up the Barnes-Hut algorithm does take additional work, but in practice this is negligible. This algorithm however also prevents us from using the reflexive property, that repulsion forces between nodes can be mirrored. This prevents us from halving the number of computations required.

The Barnes-Hut algorithm stores the points in an octree, which is a tree-like subdivision of a space. Each node in the octree represents a cubic section of space, and has 8 child nodes. These child nodes each represent a cubic subspace of the parent node, and together cover the entire space of their parent. Only nodes with an element have their children generated, and new nodes are generated on demand. Leaf nodes at maximum depth have a list of all nodes that are added to this node. The root node of an octree spans the entire space, and is initially empty. When a graph-node position is inserted into a tree-node, the center of mass of this node is computed by computing the average position of all its nodes.

The algorithm can be configured with a parameter θ . A high θ increases the performance, but lowers the accuracy of the simulation. A θ of 0 effectively reduces the heuristic to an exact computation.

The original paper introducing the Barnes-Hut algorithm suggest that a θ of 0.5 is effective for most applications. As we are less interested in the accuracy of the simulation, we experimented with higher values for θ . We found that a θ of 1.0 gives a good approximation of the layout, compared to a layout without Barnes-Hut. Artefacts started to appear on higher values.

When particles in an octree are moving, they quickly invalidate the octree. There are two ways of solving this. Either, we update the octree by extensively bookkeeping the movement of the particles, or rebuilding the graph from scratch.

Graphs	Early without	Early with	Reduction early	Late without	Late with	Reduction late
alma	0.0913	0.0173	81%	0.0954	0.0151	84%
bakery	0.0504	0.00900	82%	0.0524	0.00965	82%
leader	0.00976	0.00348	64%	0.01076	0.00378	65%
lift	0.1614	0.0171	89%	0.1541	0.0174	89%
minepump	0.00322	0.00140	56%	0.00298	0.00145	51%
twilight	0.0167	0.00514	69%	0.0195	0.00501	74%

Table 1: Iteration times in seconds for different graphs

As rebuilding the graph is the least effort, we first experimented with that setup, and found that doing so takes between 10% and 20% of the total iteration time. This means that any improvement would reduce the running time with the given percentage at best.

Assume d is the maximum degree of the nodes in a graph, and h is the depth of the octree. To build the octree we have to perform h comparisons for each node, resulting in a runtime of $O(h*N)$, assuming that inserting two nodes in one leaf is constant time. Some of these insertions require the addition of a new section of the octree, but this is a constant-time operation.

The number of computations for the forces on one node depend on the current state of the graph. In the worst case, all nodes are in one leaf of the octree, such that the Barnes-Hut heuristic has no effect. In the best case, all nodes but this node are in one section of the octree, far enough away such that one computation is executed after h comparisons. Neither of these situations are likely to occur, especially after some iterations of the force directed algorithm.

Measurements To see whether this heuristic is effective, we measure the time it takes to compute one iteration with and one without Barnes-Hut. If Barnes-Hut is an effective approximation, we expect to see a reduction of run-time.

We assume Barnes-Hut performs better when the nodes are far apart, as distant octree nodes reduce computation time. Thus we expect a difference in running time between early and late iterations for experiments with Barnes-Hut.

We assume that most graphs are nearing equilibrium after 1000 iterations. However, running 1000 iterations per experiment takes time, and 100 iterations should already make enough difference to have effect. As the running time of a single iteration is sensitive to many factors, we measure the average of the first 4 and the last 4 iterations of an experiment. We refer to the mean of the first 4 iterations as the *Early* measurements, and the mean of the last 4 iterations as the *Late* measurements.

The initial layout is random, such that all nodes are placed in a small area around the origin. We assume that the exact initial layout has only a minor impact on the iteration running time, as the nodes are all close together. We repeat each experiment 10 times, and we report on the mean running times.

We run this experiment on the graphs shown in Figure 5, and the results are shown in Figure 8. These are executed *With* and *Without* the Barnes-Hut heuristic. The iteration times and the calculated reduction fraction are shown in Table 1.

The measurements show a consistent difference between the two algorithms. Using the Barnes-Hut heuristic results in reductions between 51% and 90% of running time for this selection of graphs. We also notice that larger graphs have more time reduction than smaller graphs. This is to be expected, as the heuristic is more effective when there are multiple nodes on large distance from each other.

Figure 8: Iteration times with (grey, yellow) and without (blue, orange) Barnes-Hut optimisation.

The difference in running times between the early iterations and the late iterations is minor. We conclude that for both algorithms the iteration times do not change significantly over time.

For large graphs in general, we conclude that Barnes-Hut offers a major improvement in running time.

While experimenting, we found an edge case where the Barnes-Hut heuristic significantly increases the running time of the algorithm. This edge case is when all nodes are concentrated in a small area, and multiple nodes are positioned in the same spot. The octree would use its full depth to place all nodes, and none of the nodes are combined in the computation. This did not occur in our experiments, because we used a random initial layout, and because the force directed algorithm always progresses away from this scenario. Additionally, this situation is quickly dissolved by the effect of the force directed layout.

The computation of the net force on a single node can trivially be split into independent jobs, if we ignore the symmetry of the attraction and repulsion forces. This allows us to run these computations in parallel, providing an advantage when used in high-end processors.

6.4 High Dimensional Embedding

The other layout category is the static layout, which computes the layout in a single pass. The algorithm we consider is the High Dimensional Embedding algorithm as described by D. Harel and Y. Koren [9].

The High Dimensional Embedding algorithm (HDE) computes a high-dimensional layout using a simple algorithm, then projects this high-dimensional layout into a 2D or 3D space. The result is a reasonably effective graph layout in very short time.

The algorithm accepts a graph, a parameter *numTargetDimensions* for the target number of dimensions, and a parameter *m* that represents the number of dimensions of the high-dimensional layout, and can be increased to improve the layout quality. To represent the *m*-dimensional position of the nodes, they are assigned an *m*-dimensional vector.

The algorithm starts with picking a random node. For each node in the graph we calculate the distance of the shortest path to the current node, ignoring edge directions, and store this as the first element of its coordinate. A new node is chosen, one that is the furthest from all previously picked nodes. For each node we calculate the distance to the new current node, and store this as the next element of its coordinate. We continue picking new nodes until all m elements of the node positions are filled in. Each node now has an m -dimensional coordinate.

If we compute the three axes in this point cloud with the highest distribution of points, we can use those as the 3 axes of our projection. Doing so will result in the projection of this data where points are most spread out.

To do this, we calculate the covariance matrix of the high-dimensional coordinates, and compute the principal components of this matrix. The principal components are vectors representing the axis of the original matrix where the data is the most uniformly distributed. We then compute the new 3-dimensional coordinates of the nodes by multiplying the high-dimensional coordinates with the matrix composed of the normalized principal components.

The layout generated by this algorithm may in some cases place elements of the graph on the same position. This makes this layout problematic on those cases, and can cause major confusion.

While the algorithm is very fast, the layout is unlikely to be effective enough for analysis.

6.5 Combined technique

The force directed layout algorithm improves an existing layout, and HDE quickly generates a sub-optimal layout. We researched whether these two algorithms can be combined, using HDE to generate the initial layout of the force directed algorithm.

For this combined algorithm, we want to prove the following hypotheses:

Hypothesis 1 *The combined layout algorithm is generally faster than a pure force directed layout algorithm*

Hypothesis 2 *The combined layout algorithm produces generally better quality than a pure HDE layout*

Whether the combined algorithm is faster than the pure force directed algorithm depends on how ‘far’ the HDE result is from a force equilibrium. The quality of the combined algorithm may also change based on the initial layout. The random layout is only randomized in a small area around the origin, as the force directed algorithm is faster at expanding a graph than contracting one. Hence, the HDE layout may result in an equilibrium which a random layout would not be able to reach.

Measuring speed The force directed algorithm stabilizes when the magnitude of the net force on every node nears zero. The mean magnitude of all net forces gives an indication of how far the algorithm is from stabilizing. Hence, we can quantify the convergence of the force directed algorithm using this mean magnitude. Using this, we can quantify the speed benefit of using HDE as initial layout.

Measuring quality The forces in the force directed algorithm each work toward satisfying one ideal layout requirement. Even in equilibrium, there may be large forces acting on a single node, which are still resulting in a zero net force. This indicates that there are conflicting requirements for this node, and the current position is the best trade-off for this node.

There may be multiple graph layouts in equilibrium, but the total forces on their nodes will be different. This can be interpreted as some layouts being closer to the ideal layout than others. When we consider layout quality, we may use the sum of all force magnitudes on all nodes as indication of layout quality. We will refer to this total force magnitude as the *tension* of a graph. Using this, we can quantify the quality benefit of using HDE as initial layout.

To test our hypotheses, we collected the net force magnitude and tension over time for several graphs, and compared these. We use the example graphs mentioned in section 5, and seen in Figure 5. Each graph was first initialized using HDE layout, and then the iterative layout would stabilize the graph for 10 seconds. Then the graph was initialized using a random layout, and the iterative layout would again stabilize the graph for 10 seconds. As HDE is deterministic, repeating its experiment would yield the same results. Random layout is not deterministic, and thus we repeat the random experiment five times. We compare the net force and tension of the HDE and random layout, to see whether the HDE layout gives a speed or quality benefit.

The results of our experiments are shown in Figure 9 and Figure 10. Note that the y-axis is using a log-scale to reduce the effect of the exponential reduction of these forces. The blue line is the result of the HDE layout, the black line is the average of the random layouts. The red lines indicate a 95% confidence interval of the random layout results.

We included the interval in the graphs as a visual indication for the variance of the measurements. The confidence interval assumes a normal distribution, which not guaranteed. In addition, the central limit theorem does not apply for a sample size this small.

We will discuss the figures for each graph separately.

Alma Both the net force and tension stabilize quicker than the random layout. The tension graph eventually shows only a minor difference, which indicates that the final layout is comparable in quality.

Bakery The static layout does not appear to offer any improvement here.

The blue spot in Figure 9a is caused by vibrations in the graph. This is caused by the large number of edges connected to the initial state. As each edge exerts a force on the node, the net force is large enough to cause vibrations.

Leader The quality of a random layout seems to improve much faster than the initial layout. Eventually they reach the same tension, as both method reach the exact same layout. The net forces are approximately equal over time.

Lift This graph has a spread-out equilibrium, which the static layout is able to exploit immensely. The layout stabilizes faster and the quality is always better compared to the random layout.

Minepump The static layout reaches high quality with only a few iterations, and ends slightly better than the random layout as well. This layout also stabilizes quicker. The vibrations seen on the net force graph are the result of the low values and the log scale. These vibrations are common, but usually too small to see.

(a) Alma net force

(b) Alma tension

(c) Bakery net force

(d) Bakery tension

(e) Leader net force

(f) Leader tension

(g) Lift net force

(h) Lift tension

(i) Minepump net force

(j) Minepump tension

Figure 9: Layout tension and net force results (1/2)

Figure 10: Layout tension and net force results (2/2)

Twilight While the initial layout is more stable than the random layout, the random layout quickly overtakes in quality. The reason is that the initial static layout creates a torus with a radius larger than the stable layout. As seen here, the layout algorithm better supports growing a torus than shrinking it. This is also evident in the net force; there are less forces on the initial layout, despite it having a higher total tension.

6.6 Conclusion

The layout converges much faster in half of the cases. In the other cases there was no significant difference, and in one case the convergence was slower. Because of this, we cannot make a definite statement about the speed benefit of using HDE as the initial layout.

The reasoning that tension relates directly to graph quality is disputable. The tension describes how well the graph balances the forces of the iterative algorithm, but a minimum of these forces is not necessarily a maximisation of graph clarity. Significant graph tension can be used as indication of a low graph quality, but for small differences it should not be used as the only metric.

To get a subjective comparison on the layout quality, we added questions on layout quality in the survey. This should give us additional data on the layout quality.

7 Graph Coloring and Shaping

Whether a graph is easy to understand depends on the visual complexity, and the visibility of patterns. Indicators that help to recognize patterns often also increase the visual complexity, and require a trade-off.

We will discuss several methods to visualise the structure of the graph, and how we can use colors to support specific use cases. We also discuss how these graphical elements can be combined in a way that they do not interfere with each other.

7.1 Action highlighting

Edges with the same action label often have a certain pattern in the state space. When there are multiple parallel processes, the edges will form a grid in the state space. Different sections of the graph may also have similar behaviours, forming symmetric sections. Edges with the same actions will have the same pattern in each symmetric section.

Figure 11: A section of a graph with one action highlighted

We experimented with highlighting actions, to show how these actions are structured throughout a graph and to help recognizing these patterns. In asynchronous sections, all edges run parallel in a grid pattern, which becomes clear when these edges are colored according to their actions. Symmetric graph sections will have symmetric color patterns, making them easier to recognize and find which actions are different between them.

Our initial design consisted of assigning each action a unique color, which is effective in showing the overall structure of the graph. However, this increases the visual complexity of the graph a lot, and the overall effect is minimized. We also use colors in different parts of the visualisation for other techniques as well, so a visualisation that only uses one color is preferable.

Instead, we researched the effect of highlighting all edges with the same action as the edge that is hovered over. This only requires a single color, and reduces the visual complexity of the graph. An example of this technique can be seen in Figure 11.

Users should also be able to find specific actions in the graph without having to search for it in the graph. To support this, we allowed the user to select a specific action from a list, which is then highlighted. We experimented with a setup where the list-selected permanent highlight was distinct from the hovering highlight, to prevent confusion when a permanent highlighted action is also hovered. The permanent highlight of actions may also be toggled by clicking an edge. This showed to be a very practical way to quickly mark actions during analysis.

We found that this approach was at least as effective as assigning unique colors, and is a valuable addition to a visualisation. We expect that *action highlighting reduces the time it takes to find asynchronous and symmetric structures in the graph*. However, testing this would require a large scale survey, which we do not currently have access to. Instead, we consider a more relaxed, but testable hypothesis:

Hypothesis 3 *Action highlighting is considered helpful for recognizing asynchronous and symmetric structures in the graph.*

Figure 12: Edge shape examples

7.2 Edge shapes

The shape of edges in the graph make a difference in how easy it is to follow traces in a graph. Edges are usually represented by an arrow, but there are more variations available, each with their own advantages.

We reasoned in the previous section that edges should support being hovered and clicked on. This means that edges need a certain thickness, which also makes crossing edges harder to distinguish. To counter this, we decided to make edges semi-transparent. Overlapping edges now create a darker area on the place of overlap, and the density of crossing edges in the graph is easily seen.

In addition, there may be multiple edges between each pair of nodes. In order to position these edges to not overlap, we have to add a curve to the edges. This curve can be implemented in multiple ways, but the differences are minimal. We decided to consider the bézier curve for its ease of implementation.

We considered the following three edge shapes in our research. These shapes were the most promising shapes according to our preparatory study. These shapes are also shown in Figure 12.

- Standard arrows consisting of a line with a head at the end. This shape is the most common and easy to understand.
- Tapered lines, where the arrow head is extended to the source state. This makes a clear and simple visual distinction between the start, middle and end of an arrow.
- Gradients, where the line fades to the tip. This has a similar effect as tapered lines, but differences in thickness can be applied better.

Shape drawing procedure The edge shapes described above are 2-dimensional, but we want to apply these shapes to a 3D visualisation as well. To accurately display a 2-dimensional image in 3-dimensional space, we compute the shape using projections. We will explain this procedure here in detail.

We first transform the 3-dimensional positions of the edge into view-space. When transforming positions to view-space, we get the position of that vector relative to the camera. This allows us to ignore the z-axis, and construct the 2-dimensional image on the xy-plane.

We designed an OpenGL shader program that accepts a description of a curve in 3-dimensional world-space, and maps this to a 2-dimensional shape in screen-space. We will explain the procedure by giving a mathematical formula for the shape generation.

We used a quadratic bézier curve to describe the curve of our shape. Given three vectors A , B and C , the curve for one particular shape can be given as a mathematical function for $u \in [0, 1]$:

$$b(u) = A * (1 - u)^2 + B * 2u(1 - u) + C * u^2$$

The curve of any edge can thus be described by giving values for A , B and C . We also need to know the tangent of this curve along the direction, and for this we use the derivative. The derivative of the bézier curve is given for the same u :

$$d(u) = 2(1 - u) * (B - A) + 2u * (C - B)$$

Each of the three edge shapes can individually be described by a function that maps a point along the length of the shape to the width on that point. Assuming the shape is symmetric, we can describe these shapes as a function $f : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ that maps a value between 0 and 1 to the width of the shape. We let $f(0)$ represent the start of the shape and $f(1)$ represent the end of the shape.

These two functions $b(u)$ and $f(u)$ both accept the same parameter: a value where 0 represents the start of the edge and where 1 represents the end. We can combine these two functions to generate a description for the edge shape in 2 dimensions. To use this function for rendering shapes, we should include the perspective of the observer, to generate a shape in 2 dimensions. This allows us to implement the function in a shader, resulting in an efficient shape generation.

It should be mentioned that in graphics, positions and directions are both represented by a 4-dimensional vector. The fourth element is 1 when this vector represents a position, and 0 when a direction is represented. Transformation matrices are 4 by 4 as well, where the 4th column describes a translation. Doing so allows the same transformation matrix to transform both position and direction vectors. After all, the 4th column of a matrix has no effect on a vector where the 4th element is 0.

Before we can give the complete formulas, we have to introduce a number of required parameters. We first introduce the matrix V . This matrix represents the view matrix, and represents the transformation from world-space to view-space. Multiplying a vector with V gives this vector from the perspective of the camera. The concepts of world-space and view-space will be further explained in section 9.1.

We introduce the function $n : V \rightarrow V$, which normalizes a vector: $n(v) = \hat{v} = \frac{v}{\|v\|}$

Lastly we define matrix Z :

$$Z = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

This matrix projects a given vector on the z -plane, and rotates by a quarter around the z -axis. This function is required to transform a vector to one that is orthogonal in the camera perspective.

A , B and C represent positions, and are thus 4-dimensional with a 4th component of 1. Note that as a result, b returns a 4 dimensional vector with a 4th component of 1, and d returns a 4

dimensional vector with a 4th component of 0. We will give two formulas in terms of matrices V , P and Z , and functions f , b , d and n .

$$j(u) = V * b(u) + f(u) * n(V * d(u) * Z)$$

$$k(u) = V * b(u) - f(u) * n(V * d(u) * Z)$$

Each formula describes one half of the edge shape. Calling these two formulas for monotonically increasing values for u between 0 and 1 gives us a list of vertices. Using each three subsequent vertices to generate a triangle results in the desired shape in view-space.

The arrow shape is generally the standard in graph visualisation, so we compare our other techniques relative to this technique. Experimenting with the different edge shapes led to the impression that the simpler tapered edges are more effective as edge shape for graphs larger than 1000 nodes. Gradient edges appear to be more effective when analysing dense graphs. We will further research this in our survey, where we consider the following hypotheses.

Hypothesis 4 *Tapered edges are generally preferred over standard arrows when analysing large graphs.*

Hypothesis 5 *Gradient edges are generally preferred over standard arrows when analysing dense graphs.*

7.3 Drawing Labels

The survey in the earlier report showed that edge labeling is very important for understanding the graph. However, adding text elements to a graph quickly increases visual complexity. We want to find a method to convey the edge information most clearly without obstructing the graph.

It is critical to prevent labels from overlapping each other, while keeping clear which label belongs to which edge. We consider a number of options:

1. Apply a force directed layout to the labels in the graph, scaling the labels down until it fits
2. Remove labels that fall behind other labels, sorting on camera distance
3. Only visualize the label of the edge being hovered by the user
4. Give each unique label a color, show the color key in the UI, and color the edges accordingly.

Option 1 could create unreadable labels, which is prevented with option 2. However, removing labels at the back may make it impossible to identify edges that are surrounded by other edges. Option 3 reduces clutter to a minimum, but also makes it hard to see the structure of the graph. The advantage of option 4 is that for graphs with many edges per action, the structure of the graph becomes very clear. Actions in an LTS graph tend to follow a structure, which becomes clear with these colors. However, this limits color usage for other goals, and could prove to be unhelpful when there are many actions.

We experimented with a combination of option 4 and option 3. As described in section 7.1, we want to color all edges in the graph with the same action as the hovered edge. This would logically combine with only showing the label of the indicated action.

Figure 13: The minepump graph where the shortest path with the purple edge is indicated

We also reasoned that the edge label doesn't necessarily have to be drawn in the graph area itself. Instead of drawing the text on top of the graph, we assign a dedicated UI element to indicate the action of the currently hovered edge. We will address the effectiveness of the UI element in our survey, where we answer the following hypothesis.

Hypothesis 6 *When analysing large state spaces, indicating edge labels in a dedicated UI element upon hovering is preferred over indicating edge labels next to the hovered edge.*

7.4 Path Visualisation

The graph shape and coloring should support tracing paths through the graph. Often the analyst wants to know whether one kind of behaviour can happen after some specific other behaviour. This results in searching a path towards some state b via some state a . We can support searching for paths by providing a tool to search for a path between any two nodes.

The user should be able to visualise a path between two nodes by just selecting them. The tool can compute the shortest path using the Breadth First Search path finding algorithm. The path can be given a specific color, and the trace can be displayed to the user. Possible alternative paths can be displayed in a second color.

As an example, we look at a graph for a methane level control system in Figure 13. We indicated the shortest path from the target state of the purple transition to the source state of the transition, forming a loop. This path shows the shortest trace of actions that is required for this particular state transition to reactivate. It gives an indication of how the behaviour flows through the graph, and what behaviour is required before the system ends in the same state a second time.

We expect that this tool is useful when answering questions about the order of possible behaviour.

Figure 14: Example situations. ϕ holds in the green state.

7.5 Semantic coloring

As we discussed in use case 4, we could support analysing properties using a reachability analysis. The paper by Barbon and Leroy [2] describes the CLEAR system, which is a coloring scheme based on a property given as a mu-calculus formula. The system colors critical states where a property becomes unavoidable or unreachable. We will discuss how we implemented the technique as described by Barbon and Leroy.

Given a formula ϕ , we can compute the set of states S that satisfy formula ϕ . We can also compute the set of states P from where such a state is unavoidable by computing which states satisfy $\mu X.(\phi \vee (\langle true \rangle true \wedge [true]X))$. Similarly, we can compute the set of states Q from where such a state is unreachable by computing $\nu X.(\neg \phi \wedge [true]X)$. The techniques used to compute the set of states that satisfy these formulas are outside the scope of our thesis.

We have two example graphs in figure 14, where ϕ holds in s_1 of both graphs. In figure 14a, P consists of s_2 , and Q is empty. In figure 14b, P is empty and Q consists of s_3 and s_5 .

Notice that a state cannot be in both P and Q . Additionally, set Q is closed: no edge exist that starts in Q , and ends outside Q .

If a state has a path into S , then S can be reached from that state and this state is not in Q . This is the case for all states in figure 14a.

If a state has a path to itself that doesn't contain states of S , then S can be avoided and this state is not in P . This is the case for states s_3 , s_4 and s_5 in figure 14a.

Trivially, if a state has no outgoing edges, then all states but itself are unreachable, and all states but itself can be avoided. Hence, deadlocked states where the property holds are in P , and those where the property does not hold are in Q .

Some edges are of particular interest. We first consider edges with a source state outside P and a target state within P . Whenever the system executes such transition, the property ϕ becomes unavoidable. In figure 14a, the transition (s_4, s_2) is such a transition.

Similarly, there are edges with a source state outside Q and a target state within Q . Executing such transition makes a property ϕ become unreachable. In figure 14b, the transition (s_1, s_3) is such transition.

Because a state cannot be both in P and Q , these two edge groups are always distinct.

To formally define critical edges, we introduce the notion of S -critical for arbitrary sets S .

Definition 16 *Let $A = \langle S, T, L \rangle$ be a labelled transition system. Let there be a set $S' \subseteq S$. An edge $(a, b) \in E$ is considered S' -critical, if $a \notin S' \wedge b \in S'$.*

We want to visualise the P -critical edges for making the property unavoidable, and we want to visualize the Q -critical states for making the property unreachable. This should make it clear what behaviour leads to the property, and help understand how the property is reflected in the model.

We will address the effectiveness in our survey, where we try to confirm the following hypothesis.

Hypothesis 7 *Coloring the critical edges of a property helps finding errors in the formal model, and helps understanding how a property is represented in the graph.*

8 Complexity Reduction

A third way of improving graph readability is to reduce the size of the graph. While this is not always an option, there are often situations where not all information displayed in the graph is significant. We present a number of techniques that reduce the graph complexity, and show how these techniques can be combined. These techniques differ in what they remove, and how the new graph is presented.

Each of these techniques assume a set of actions that the user has marked as unimportant. These are often actions that describe functionality that runs asynchronous to the remainder of the system, or describe specific steps in the process that are not important for the current analysis. We will assume for this section an arbitrary graph $A = \langle S, T, L \rangle$. We assume set $U \in L$ contains all actions that are marked unimportant, and $T_U \in T$ as the set of transitions with an action label in U .

8.1 Action hiding

The most straightforward method is to make all edges in T_U transparent. Activating this method does not affect the layout of the graph. An example is given in figure 15a.

This is especially effective when the unimportant edges are obscuring inner parts of the graph. As these edges should be ignored, it helps when these edges can not be selected or clicked on.

8.2 Clustering on Actions

Clustering on actions is a technique where we cluster all states that are connected with transitions in T_U . Node connection is transitive: when three nodes are connected with transitions in T_U , they are reduced to one state. An example is given in figure 15b

These clusters will however not entirely represent the original states in terms of transitions. Transition paths that seem possible through clusters may not be possible in the original graph. In figure 16, the left graph does not allow a path from $s1$ to $s4$. After clustering on action b , there exists a path from $s1$ to $s4$.

Figure 15: A graph section with two complexity reduction techniques

Figure 16: An example where clustering makes certain paths possible

Figure 17: A section of graph with τ -actions

This clustering can be achieved by traversing T_U , and cluster the nodes of each transition $(s_0, s_1) \in T_U$. To cluster two nodes s_0 and s_1 , one deletes s_0 and redirects the edges as follows: for arbitrary node $s_i \in S$, we transform every edge (s_0, s_i) into (s_1, s_i) and every edge (s_i, s_0) into (s_i, s_1) .

We considered it important to allow the user to quickly switch between the clustered and normal graph. To make the two graphs visually similar, we compute the position of the clustered nodes based on the positions of the unclustered nodes. In this way, all nodes that are not part of a cluster do not change position.

The alternative is to apply the layout algorithm on the clustered graph. This approach allows a faster layout for large graphs, as the layout algorithm is executed on fewer nodes.

We implemented both approaches, and allow toggling between the two at any time. When the layout algorithm is applied on the clustered graph, we forward the movement of the clusters to the original nodes.

We will address the effectiveness of this technique in our survey, where we consider the following hypothesis:

Hypothesis 8 *Attribute clustering increases graph readability when the model contains asynchronous elements.*

8.3 Clustering on Confluence

LTS graphs often contain actions that represent internal behaviour. These actions, referred to as τ -actions, are in many situations not interesting for the analysis, and can be ignored. However, clustering these actions as described in the previous section may result in a graph with a different behaviour. We have seen this in figure 16.

To illustrate further, we consider an extreme example where the majority of the edges represent internal behaviour. The section of graph we see in Figure 17 shows a graph where all edges not representing τ -actions are colored yellow. If we would cluster this section on τ edges, this entire section would collapse into two edges. However, this collapsed section would not represent the behaviour of the system because some τ -actions change what future actions are possible.

It is often not desired to ignore τ -actions entirely, but rather to remove τ -actions that result in the same branching behaviour. One popular method of reducing the graph complexity in

this regard is a reduction preserving branching bisimulation. As described in section 15, a branching bisimulation handles τ -actions differently.

Two states are τ -confluent when they are connected with a τ -action, and their branching behaviour is identical. Reducing these two states to one state will result in a graph that is branching bisimilar to the original graph.

In Figure 17a, one group of confluent states are indicated blue. All these states are branching bisimilar, indicating that they have the same branching behaviour when ignoring τ -actions. Successfully clustering confluent states results in a graph that is smaller, but behaviourally equivalent to the original graph.

To find the classes of confluent states, we consider the algorithm described by Groote and Van de Pol [7]. This algorithm computes the set of confluent transitions T_{conf} using algorithm 4. From the set of confluent transitions, we can compute which elements are in the same equivalence class.

The algorithm takes a description of a graph, as a set of nodes N and a set of edges T . The algorithm starts with a stack containing all transitions, and a set of candidate confluent transitions which contains all τ transitions in T . Now, as long as the stack is not empty, we take a transition $s_0 \xrightarrow{a} s_1$ from the stack, and check whether this transition is confluent with respect to all candidate transitions starting from s_0 . Any candidate transitions that is not confluent with this transition is removed from the set of candidate transitions. When this happens for any candidate, all transitions $p \xrightarrow{a} s_0$, which are predecessors of $s_0 \xrightarrow{a} s_1$, are pushed back on the stack. Once the stack is empty, the set of candidate transitions are all τ -confluent. All states connected by these transitions are in the same confluence group.

Algorithm 4 Computing confluence

```

1: procedure COMPUTECONFLUENTTRANSITIONS( $S, T$ )
2:   Stack stack  $\leftarrow T$ 
3:   Set candidates  $\leftarrow$  all  $\tau$  edges in  $T$ 
4:   while stack is not empty do
5:     take element  $t = s_0 \xrightarrow{a} s_1$  from stack
6:     anyFail  $\leftarrow$  false
7:     for all transitions  $o = s_0 \xrightarrow{\tau} s_2$  in candidates do
8:        $isConfluent \leftarrow$  CHECKCONFLUENCE( $t, o, \mathbf{CANDIDATES}$ )
9:       if  $!isConfluent$  then
10:        remove  $o$  from candidates
11:        anyFail  $\leftarrow$  true
12:     if anyFail then
13:       add all transitions  $p \rightarrow s_0$  to stack
14:   return candidates

```

To check whether a transition $s_0 \xrightarrow{a} s_1$ is confluent with respect to a candidate transition $s_0 \xrightarrow{\tau} s_2$, one of the following 4 properties must hold.

- $a = \tau \wedge s_1 = s_2$
- $a = \tau \wedge$ a transition $s_1 \xrightarrow{\tau} s_2$ exists in **candidates**
- transition $s_2 \xrightarrow{a} s_1$ exists

- for some $s_3 \in S$, there exists a transition $s_2 \xrightarrow{a} s_3$, and a candidate $s_1 \xrightarrow{\tau} s_3$.

This is checked in algorithm 5: CHECKCONFLUENCE.

Algorithm 5 Check edge confluence

```

1: procedure CHECKCONFLUENCE( $t, o, \text{candidates}$ )
2:   let  $t = s_0 \xrightarrow{a} s_1$ 
3:   let  $o = s_0 \xrightarrow{\tau} s_2$ 
4:   if  $a = \tau \wedge s_1 = s_2$  then
5:     return true ▷ any edge is confluent with itself
6:   if  $a = \tau \wedge$  a transition  $s_1 \xrightarrow{\tau} s_2$  exists in candidates then
7:     return true
8:   if there exists a transition  $s_2 \rightarrow s_1$  then
9:     return true
10:  for all transitions  $s_1 \xrightarrow{\tau} s_3$  in candidates do
11:    if there exists a transition  $s_2 \rightarrow s_3$  then
12:      return true
13:  return false

```

In total, the running time of the algorithm to compute the set of confluent transitions on a graph $A = \langle S, T, L \rangle$ is $O(|T| * Fanout_\tau^3)$.

First, the subroutine CHECKCONFLUENCE takes $O(Fanout_\tau^2)$ steps: for each transition $s_0 \xrightarrow{\tau} s_1$, we have to check the outgoing τ transitions of s_1 . Using a mapping of outgoing transitions, finding these transitions is linear, hence it depends on the square of the τ -fanout.

Every transition $s_0 \xrightarrow{a} s_1$ is put on the stack at most $Fanout_\tau + 1$ times: once initially, and once whenever the candidate of a τ -successor of s_1 is reset. As we look at $|T|$ transitions, this results in a running time of $O(|T| * Fanout_\tau^3)$.

A note on optimisation can be made for lines 6 and 10 of algorithm 5: CHECKCONFLUENCE. In both cases, we have to look up the transitions $s_1 \xrightarrow{\tau} s_3$ in **candidates**, which is independent of the parameter o . Hence we can pre-compute this collection after line 5 of algorithm 4: COMPUTECONFLUENTTRANSITIONS.

We can give each equivalence class a unique color, which is very effective in showing the overall structure of the graph. However, as we discussed in Edge Highlighting, we rather minimize the number of colors used. Again, we can choose to only show equivalence classes when hovered on. With this approach, we color all nodes in an equivalence class with a predefined color when any of the nodes are selected. The result is the same as seen in Figure 17a, where all confluent nodes are colored blue.

Rather than indicating confluent groups, we can also cluster all nodes of a single confluent group. The result is shown in Figure 17b.

We want to test either of these approaches in our survey, where we consider two hypotheses.

Hypothesis 9 *Showing confluent groups of states helps to understand behavioural similarities between states.*

Hypothesis 10 *Clustering confluent states helps to understand behavioural similarities between states.*

9 Graph Rendering

To visualize large graphs, we also need a rendering method that is capable of rendering all visualisations within reasonable time. To achieve this, we designed an advanced rendering procedure specifically for rendering graphs using the techniques in our research.

We first describe in general terms how a regular graphics rendering procedure works, and the different perspective that we make use of in our algorithm. We will describe two existing techniques for rendering a graph, and a third technique that we designed for our use case.

We will use OpenGL in our tool, in accordance to the OpenGL 3.3 specification. This specification describes how the GPU can be programmed to apply custom data manipulations.

9.1 Rendering pipeline

We will first describe how object data, commonly referred to as a mesh, is processed by a series of shader programs, which ultimately draw on the screen buffer.

The mesh can be considered as a list of data blocks, where each data block contains the information for a single vertex. In a general 3D object visualisation, a data block contains vertex positions, normals and texture coordinates. These data blocks are processed in 4 distinctive steps, 3 of which can be modified.

Step 1 : the vertex processor This step allows per-vertex modification. This step is often used to transform vertices to the camera perspective.

Step 2 : the geometry processor This step combines vertices into triangles. The general application takes 3 vertices and outputs those as a triangle.

Step 3 : the rasterisation processor This step projects the triangles on the screen, and splits it into pixels. This step cannot be modified.

Step 4 : the fragment processor This step takes interpolated vertex data, and computes the color of the pixel. This step is generally used to apply textures and shadow effects to objects.

Transformations The mesh is commonly encoded as a solid object, centered in its own coordinate system. This coordinate system is referred to as the **model-space**. The mesh will be transformed to multiple other coordinate systems, each of which has some properties that we will exploit in our custom rendering procedure. This transformation usually happens in the vertex processor, but may also happen in the geometry processor.

On the first transformation, these vertex positions are transformed to their position in the virtual world, bringing them to **world-space**. Next, all node positions are rotated to be relative to the camera, bringing them to **view-space**. A perspective warp and a scaling is applied to introduce a perspective, bringing the vertices to **screen-space**.

From this situation, we consider the cube centered on $(0, 0, 0)$ with sides of length 2 as the visible portion of the world. The z -axis is considered the depth of the scene, and the (x, y) coordinates are mapped to the screen pixel coordinates. As a result, only vertices in screen space with all of their elements between -1 and 1 are visible on the screen. Internal to the graphics driver, these relative positions are transformed to actual screen pixels before the rasterisation process.

This process can be executed on the CPU, and systems without a graphics card do so. However, a GPU can utilize the high degree of parallelism that this system has by design. Each element in a single processor step can be executed in parallel, even using SIMD instructions (Single Instruction Multiple Data) for the most part. This also means that the rendering process becomes more efficient on the GPU when there are more elements in a single GPU call.

9.2 Techniques

We researched techniques for rendering large graphs based on OpenGL 3.3. We also discuss a solution we developed ourselves, that draws graphs with minimal GPU interaction.

Naive Rendering Common rendering techniques handle movement and animations by applying transformations on static objects. The specifics of these transformations are written to the GPU before rendering.

With this technique, one can render a graph using a ‘node’ mesh and an ‘edge’ mesh. Using smart scaling and transforming, these meshes can be transformed to the correct positions and directions. For edges, we can create an arrow head mesh, and use built-in line generation functions for the body.

The result is however far from optimal. When an element is rendered, its position and other properties are loaded into the GPU before the rendering procedure starts. Writing the transformation of a single mesh to the GPU takes a relatively significant time, which mounts up noticeably when it happens 10 000 times per frame.

These problems occur for any solution that involves placing nodes and edges individually.

One Mesh Rendering To circumvent writing transformations, one can precompute the transformations for each element. This data is then loaded into a new mesh, which is unique for each node.

These data chunks can also be combined into a single mesh, to reduce interactions even further. The singular resulting shape is visually equal to the separate parts, and renders faster.

The main disadvantage, however, is that any changes to the shape cannot easily be propagated. Changing the shape of the mesh is equivalent to writing a new mesh and discarding the current. The time required to write a mesh to the GPU depends on the size of the mesh in bytes, and becomes noticeable for meshes of a few kilobytes.

Custom Shader Rendering The one-mesh solution can however be made viable if we can reduce the size of the mesh. We developed a rendering solution that generates the geometry of the elements based on position and color data.

We have one mesh describing all nodes, and one describing all edges. Each is rendered with a different set of shaders. The entire rendering procedure uses a constant number of OpenGL calls, for minimal interaction. Additionally, the number of elements in each call is large, maximizing the use of hardware acceleration.

We discuss the implementation next.

9.3 Custom shader implementation

Our solution renders the graph using two separate, dedicated sets of shaders, each accepting their own custom data formats. This technique should allow efficient graph rendering, even when the graph shape changes after every rendered frame. We discuss the technique by describing the data formats, and the operations executed by each shader step.

Nodes The node mesh contains the position and colors of each node.

The geometry shader operates on one vertex only. The shader starts by taking the node position and transforming it to view-space. Using an array of predefined offsets, we generate triangles with two neighbouring offsets and the middle vertex.

For each triangle, the middle vertex receives a `distanceToCenter` marking of 0, while all others receive a marking of 1. In the fragment shader, this `distanceToCenter` value is interpolated, and each fragment receives an approximation of its relative distance to the center of the circle. We use this value to color every pixel with a `distanceToCenter` larger than 0.9 as black, while coloring the remainder according to the vertex color.

Edges The edge mesh contains the positions of both nodes, the position of the edge handle that determines the bending of the edge, and the edge color.

The geometry shader calculates the quadratic bezier curve described by the three node positions. On a predetermined number of positions along this curve, we add a section of arrow. This is achieved by calculating the vector orthogonal to the curve, re-scaling it to the appropriate offset, and generating the resulting triangles. The exact shape can be implemented depending on user preference.

The fragment shader fills the geometry with the color according to the mesh data, with an optional interpolated transparency for gradients. If no transparency is specified, it assumes a half-transparent grey. The transparency helps detect overlap between edges, and to better distinguish between multiple overlapping arrows.

Change propagation Whenever the positions or colors change, the node and edge meshes must be reloaded. This is generally slow, but still outweighs a per-node rendering approach. To accelerate updating the graph, we store our mesh data using the OpenGL data hint `STREAM_DRAW`. This data hint indicates to the GPU driver that the data is likely to change often.

Interaction We discuss clicking and hovering nodes and edges in our techniques, and thus our rendering procedure must support these interactions as well. To support user interaction, we must be able to find what element is visible on the mouse pointer screen coordinates. As our visualisation is computed entirely by the GPU, we have to use the rendering procedure for this.

Our solution is to render the scene a second time on a separate render buffer, with a slight alteration. This render buffer is a data block in memory that will not be written to the screen. Hence, as we render into this buffer, the user will not see the result.

We modified our shaders such that when the `render_unique` flag is active, each element in the geometry shader receives a unique color. The specific color of each element is chosen to represent the element index in binary.

Once a scene is rendered, we can check the pixel color of the coordinate of the pointer and compute the graph element index that results in this color.

We decided to use color values in increments of four, to prevent minor rounding errors. As we are using 6 bits of three colors, we can assign 262 144 unique colors.

The main disadvantage of this method is that the scene has to be rendered twice each frame. The modified rendering pass could be rendered to a lower resolution than the real frame, to reduce rendering times.

Graphs	Nodes static	Nodes dynamic	Edges static	Edges dynamic
alma	1 560	2 487	3 864	5 411
bakery	1 327	2 114	2 396	3 461
leader	1 124	1 564	1 353	2 015
lift	1 569	4 018	2 799	6 173
minepump	906	1 575	728	1 191
twilight	1 195	1 752	1 761	2 458
SMS	4 080	4 750	20 043	26 468
WMS	12 136	12 273	98 376	120 575

Table 2: Mean time to render different graphs in microseconds

9.4 Measurements

To measure the effectiveness of this rendering procedure, we implemented it in a visualisation tool. We measure the run-time for each shader each frame, and compute the average of at least 100 frames.

Because we are mostly interested in larger graphs, we added two large graphs, *SMS* and *WMS*. The *WMS* graph originally has over a million nodes, which is much larger than we intend to support with our tool. For this reason we reduced the size of the graph to 50 000 nodes in a breadth-first approach.

SMS is a graph with 12 690 nodes and 85 100 edges, *WMS* is a graph with 50 000 nodes and 364 341 edges.

As we discussed earlier, our rendering technique is slower when the graph is moving, as the new graph data is written to the GPU. To test the differences, we run our experiments once while the graph is static, and once where the graph is updated each frame. We do not run the layout algorithm to move the graph while rendering, as this will interfere with the run-times. Instead we force the GPU to reload all position data, which has the same effect. We indicate the measurements without position update as *static* and the measurements with position update as *dynamic*.

We found after the first experiments that there are large differences in run-time depending on the zoom factor. Zooming out significantly increases the rendering speed, causing major differences between experiments on the same graph. When sufficiently zoomed out, some triangles become smaller than a pixel, and the graphics card discards them.

To prevent these differences, we reran the experiments on a fixed zoom level, chosen such that the largest graph was displayed entirely on the screen. The results are shown in table 2. We compare the runtime of the focus graphs in figure 18. We excluded *SMS* and *WMS* from this diagram, as their values are much larger than the other graphs.

The run-time for the edge shader is generally larger than for the node shader, which is as expected as edges have a more involved drawing procedure, and there are more edges than nodes.

We see that the run-time of the dynamic experiments is consistently larger than the static experiments. The increase is generally less than double, showing that the additional time to write to the GPU is reasonable.

The *SMS* graph can be rendered dynamically, updating positions each frame, in 0.0312 seconds. This corresponds to 32 frames per second. *WMS* can be rendered dynamically in 0.1328 seconds. This corresponds to 7.5 frames per second.

Figure 18: Runtime of rendering one frame of graph elements in nanoseconds

Our rendering technique is able to provide a reasonably efficient rendering procedure. While less than 20 frames per second is not enough for a smooth experience, we think it is enough to perform graph analysis. Visualising graphs of this size is often not necessary, as the zoom factor required to visualise the whole graph makes the individual elements indiscernible. More options to visualise parts of the graph should be added to assist in analysing subsections of those graph.

10 Reflection survey

We have formulated a number of hypotheses when describing the techniques. To test these hypotheses and to measure how effective the implementations are, we perform a survey.

The hypotheses that we will address in our survey are listed here.

Technique Hypotheses

Technique	Hypothesis
The combined layout algorithm	produces generally better quality than a pure HDE layout.
Action highlighting	helpful for recognizing asynchronous structures in the graph.
Tapered edges	generally preferred over standard arrows when analysing large graphs.
Gradient edges	generally preferred over standard arrows when analysing dense graphs.
Dedicated label UI	preferred over indicating edge labels next to the hovered edge.
Attribute clustering	increases graph readability when the model contains asynchronous elements.
Semantic coloring	helps understanding how a property is represented in the graph.

This survey consists of a number of assignments, which can be completed using the tool. The assignments are chosen such that all use cases are covered in the assignments, and all assignments are directed to a specific use case. We conduct this research on the same group of users as the prestudy, as these people are experienced LTS graph analysts. The fact that we use the same group of participants, means that we can not consider these two surveys independent. However, this also means that we can compare the surveys to see how the results of the earlier survey is reflected in the results of this survey.

We appended a question on the effectiveness of visualising confluence after the second survey was submitted. This appended section only received two replies.

In this section we first describe the content of this survey, and then discuss the results.

10.1 The survey

The user receives a small set of assignments that are representative of analysis tasks. These assignments look at different types of graph, in terms of size, degree and general structure.

The tool, together with an assignment sheet is sent to the user. The assignment sheet contains a description of all functions of the tool. Some assignments may have suggestions for settings and some have imposed restrictions. This allows us to test our techniques in relative isolation.

The tool also writes performance data of the rendering and the iteration algorithm. We can use this to compare performance across multiple machines.

We created two versions of the survey. For the first version we gathered a collection of 6 LTS graphs that covers a wide variety of situations. We created questions to test the hypotheses on each of these graphs and ensured that all hypotheses were covered.

This first version was discussed with an expert in the field of formal models, where the expert would also try to answer each of the questions. Using this feedback, we removed two graphs where the questions were not up to quality

The first graph we removed was **Lift**. This graph contains a clear 3-way symmetry, and some of its subsections were also symmetric. Symmetry wasn't directly required for any hypothesis, and any question on this graph could be reformulated for other graphs.

The second graph we removed was **Bakery**. The model of this graph was infinite, and all nodes could reach the initial state within 6 transitions. This graph is an example where the force directed layout has a negative impact on the readability of the graph. The questions researched the effectiveness of the force directed layout and the usefulness of the path finding algorithm. We realized that there was no reason to argue the effectiveness of one layout algorithm in particular, as we intend to research the combined algorithm instead. We ensured that the path finding algorithm was also represented in other graphs, and removed other questions specifically about layout.

The other questions also received a rework. We now explicitly mention the tools and steps that should be used to answer each question. The questions are a means to evaluate the tools, and should not be challenging. We added additional reflection questions to reinforce our results, and get more insight in user experience with the tools.

The final set of questions are added below. The four remaining graphs are shown in Figure 5 This survey was sent to a number of formal modelling experts, of which we received four results.

Twilight

This section will test the techniques for labeling and edge visualisation. Load the graph `twilight.aut`, and set the simulation step size to maximum. Note that this graph is initially shaped as a torus, and you have to zoom out.

The twilight control system consists of two modules: a drill module, and a conditioner module. Products are moved from input via these modules to an output by a load (L) and unload (U) robot.

Question 1 Wait until the graph stabilizes. Which of the two robots does the transportation from conditioner to drill? Find the sections where the conditioner and where the drill is operated, and analyse the transitions between them.

Question 2 The two robots operate asynchronously. Do the drill and the conditioner run asynchronously with the robots? How do you know?

Question 3 Does the highlighting of action help finding the asynchronous sections of the model? Give your answer on a scale of 0 to 10, with 0 as hindering, and 10 as a necessity.

Question 4 Does the approach of the labeling in this tool hinder your search? Give your answer on a scale of 0 to 10, with 0 as near impossible, and 10 as much better than always visible labels.

Leader

This section will test the graph layout systems. Load the graph `leader.aut`, but do not change the simulation step size until asked to.

This graph is derived from the Dolev-Klawe-Rodeh leader selection algorithm. The algorithm, is used to select a leader from a ring of autonomous units using identifiers. During the procedure, the active units send each other messages asynchronously, and the number of active units decreases overtime. Eventually, only one unit is active, who elects itself leader.

Question 1 As each unit is executing the same program, there should be a network of asynchronous steps in the graph. This should be visible as a gridlike structure of interleaved actions. Does the initial layout show this grid structure?

Question 2 Set the simulation step size to maximum, and wait until the graph stabilizes. Does the new layout show the gridlike structure better? Does it offer an improvement on the initial layout or are there shortcomings?

Question 3 In this graph, there are more than 3 units executing asynchronously. Does the highlighting of action labels help understanding which parts of this model are asynchronous? Give your answer on a scale of 0 to 10, with 0 as hindering, and 10 as a necessity.

Question 4 In `Display Options`, set the edge shape to `GRADIENT`. Does this representation improve the readability of the graph?

Alma

This section looks at the use of semantic graph coloring: coloring based on a mu-formula. Load the graph `alma.aut`, and set the simulation step size to maximum.

Given is the access control manager of the ALMA system. This system regulates access to containers and components using Manager threads.

Select "Load Mu-formula" and select the file "`alma.execute.mcf`". This file contains the formula `<execute(Cont1, Comp1)>true || <execute(Cont1, Comp2)>true`.

It selects all states where an `execute` action can be performed. Any edge that makes a future `execute` action unreachable is colored red. Any edge where a future `execute` action is unavoidable is colored green.

We also look at an alternative edge shape. In `Display Options`, set the edge shape to `TAPERED`.

Question 1 Select the execute actions in the list Are there edges that represent an `execute` action that can not be repeated? How do you recognize these?

Question 2 There are 4 small loops where `execute` action has become unreachable. What does this mean if the system ends up in these states?

Question 3 With which action are the loops of question 2 entered?

Question 4 Does the formula-based coloring help understanding the behaviour of this graph? Give your answer on a scale of 0 to 10, with 0 as actively confusing, and 10 as a necessity.

Question 5 Does the tapered edge shape improve the readability of the graph?

Minepump

This section looks at the clustering and following traces. Load the graph `minepump.aut`, and set the simulation step size to maximum. You may set the edge shape to any shape you prefer.

The graph describes a controller to regulate methane levels in a mineshaft.

Question 1 Does the pump system start running as reaction of a low methane level or a high methane level? Find the `pumpRunning`, `highLevel` and `lowLevel` actions, and look at how `pumpRunning` is reached. You can use the `Find shortest path` function to quickly see connectedness.

Context Highlight the actions `MethaneRise` and `MethaneLower`. You will notice that these actions occur virtually everywhere in the graph.

Set the display method to `Cluster on selected`, and cluster the selected actions using the "C" button. This will collapse those actions, combining each pair of nodes into a clustered node.

Question 2 Consider again the question whether the pump system start running on high or low level. Does this clustering improve the readability of the graph?

Reflection

As you have done a few tasks with the tool, we want to hear your opinion on some of the basic elements. If you think that the answer depends on the situation, please indicate in what situation the question does and does not apply.

Question 1 Would you prefer labels to be visible in the graph, rather than the solution presented in the tool?

Question 2 Do you have a strong preference for a specific edge shape? Is there an edge shape you would not normally use?

Question 3 Did you consider using a 2D visualisation for any of the above graphs?

Alma 2

Open `alma.2.aut`, and set the simulation step size to maximum. In this graph, all actions are hidden, except for the synchronisation actions. When hovering over a node, all branching bisimilar nodes are also highlighted.

Question 1 Is this node highlighting effective in recognizing confluent sections? Give your answer on a scale of 0 to 10, with 0 as hindering, and 10 as helpful.

Question 2 Activate the [I] button next to the `tau` action. This will mark this action as internal, and cluster all confluent nodes. Does this clustering improve the graph readability? Give your answer on a scale of 0 to 10, with 0 as hindering, and 10 as a helpful.

Question 3 Activate the [C] button next to the `tau` action. This will collapse all tau-actions, leaving only the synchronisation actions visible. Doing so will change the behaviour of the graph, but also leaves less actions visible. Compared to the clustering on confluence, which one is more effective?

Question 4 Given that any action can be marked internal in the tool, is any of the two clustering method redundant?

10.2 Survey Results

The choice on visualisation techniques in this study was based on a survey of a previous study. We asked these participants to collaborate with our current study, and received a total of 4 responses. While this number is statistically insignificant, it does allow us to support our claims of effectiveness.

We will discuss some claims from the survey, and the feedback we received on them from the survey.

The combined layout algorithm produces generally better quality than a pure HDE layout.

The participants agreed that the layout improves due to the iterative layout. Grid structures become more pronounced, to some extent. This indicates that the combination of the two layout techniques provide a better layout than just a static layout.

We concluded in section 6.6 that we had no clear indication whether using HDE to generate an initial layout provides an improvement on the iterative layout convergence speed. Here we conclude that the iterative layout does improve the HDE layout quality.

The highlighting of action helps finding asynchronous sections

This claim was tested for two situations. The first situation was on the *twilight* graph, which has a clear 2-dimensional structure with 3-dimensional subsections. Action highlighting was considered very effective in confirming asynchronicity in this graph.

The second situation was on the *leader* graph, which has a number of asynchronous subsections starting and stopping with few actions in-between. In this situation, the highlighting was considered far less effective. The technique was still effective in showing the presence of asynchronicity, but the dimensionality and exact properties were hard to find.

A recurring remark was that when multiple actions are highlighted, the actions should still be distinguishable. Leaving the color choice to the user would be an effective way of doing this.

Gradient and tapered edge shapes are effective

The prestudy survey showed a preference for arrow edges. For the situations we presented in our survey however, the different edge styles were considered equally effective.

We specifically asked our users to reflect these alternative edge representations in situations where we expected them to be effective. The tapered edge was suggested to be used in the *alma* graph. Some participants remarked that tapered edges are harder to read from a distance, as they have less surface than arrows. In general however, they agreed that the direction of the edges are better visible, and that it is effective.

The gradient edge was suggested in the *leader* graph. This graph has a number of highly connected nodes, which causes visual clutter for most edges. The participants agreed that the gradient edges makes it easier to distinguish the different edges and clearly shows the general direction of edges. They were however divided on the effectiveness of showing the structure of the graph. Especially details are harder to read with gradient edges.

The dedicated label UI is preferred over indicating edge labels next to the hovered edge.

The participants agreed that for large graphs, the presented solution was better than showing all labels. However, the dedicated UI element was not considered *effective*, as it was still difficult to use. The distance between the mouse pointer and the embedded element makes it hard to quickly see the edge labels. When the edges are small due to the zoom level, the mouse pointer may also slip off before the UI element could be read.

Due to these difficulties, it was preferred that displaying the action label next to the mouse pointer is far more effective than a dedicated UI element.

Attribute clustering improves the readability of the graph

We tested graph clustering for the graph *minepump* in Figure 5e. Clustering this graph causes it to collapse in a much smaller graph. When asked to answer a question that was not related to the collapsed edges, the participants universally agreed that the clustering helped in the given situation.

The formula based coloring helps understanding how a property is represented in the graph

Formula based coloring was considered effective, but hard to use. There may not be many situations where this coloring tool is used, but it can function as an alternative to counterexamples.

Admittedly, the implementation in the tool is tedious in use, but also rather powerful. Suggestions for improvement were to visualize reachability of a given set of actions, which then can be indicated using the same system as action highlighting.

Alternatively, we could present the user with a template property where actions can be inserted. For example, some properties are formulated as **when <a> happens, must happen before <c> happens**. We could let the user define a set of actions to replace <a>, and <c>, and translate this into a mu-formula.

Indicating confluent states is useful in model development

The participants agreed that this is useful, but could use more indication. As the confluent states are by definition connected with τ -transitions, the visualisation could be more effective if these edges are highlighted as well. Clustering confluent states was also deemed very useful, as it made the graph smaller and easier to read.

Clustering on confluence is better than Attribute clustering

While attribute clustering results in a smaller graph, it also results in a slightly different behaviour than the original graph. Clustering confluent states does not have this issue, but results in a larger graph. The participants argued that both types of clustering can be used in different situations. While clustering on confluence is sufficient for development, it may still be helpful to consider the interactions of a set of actions in isolation.

A 3-dimensional layout is sufficient for large graphs

While we did not formulate an hypothesis specifically for the graph projection, we wanted to review whether a 3-dimensional projection is effective.

The graphs in the survey were graphs that can be encountered in practice. The participants agreed that for these graphs, the 3-dimensional visualisation is better than 2-dimensional visualisations.

11 Threats to validity

Performance measurements in this report are executed in the Java Virtual Machine. The JVM optimizes programs during runtime, which makes performance increase over time. This applies to the results in table 1 and table 2.

We attempted to circumvent most of this effect by starting each experiment with a redundant graph, and discard its results. There is likely still a minor bias in the remaining performance measurements.

A point could be made that in the general use case, the program is used to visualise one graph before it is closed, which implies that the graphs are generally visualised without the runtime optimisations. This difference is a small, constant-size time difference for every experiment, and the effect will be more noticeable for small graphs.

The survey is empiric, and has a very small sample size. The conclusions from the survey should not be considered as statistical findings, but as expert advise.

The graphs of the survey were chosen such that they support the techniques to be researched. Hence, the findings of the survey are a best-case scenario, and may not apply to all graphs.

In particular the edge shapes were applied to graphs where we expected them to be most effective. This is most notable for gradient edges.

Because the **leader** graph is acyclic, all edges are directed towards the end of the graph. We realize that in practical applications, this is very unlikely to happen.

When two gradient edges overlay in opposite direction, the gradients cancel each other out. A similar effect is visible in clusters with cycles and edges in all directions, as you can see in Figure 19. The general direction in this example is hardly visible.

Figure 19: A situation where gradients do not show direction

12 Conclusion

We considered 3 use case categories of state space visualisation, and presented 10 techniques that could help in these use cases. We presented two layout techniques, and analysed a combination of these two. We presented five techniques to help the structural analysis of the graph. We presented three techniques to reduce graph complexity without removing important aspects of the graph.

Section 9 describes an optimized rendering procedure that also supports all the techniques we discussed. We implemented all techniques and the rendering procedures in a tool, and used it to perform a survey on the effectiveness of the techniques.

From this research, we have formulated the following conclusions:

- 1: The combined layout algorithm** is *generally* faster than a pure force based algorithms. While all tested graphs reached a reasonable quality in short time, some graphs took longer than a random initialized layout to stabilize. These slower situations were never problematic, and the benefit in faster situations was large.
- 2: The combined layout algorithm** *does* produce better quality than a pure HDE layout. The survey participants agreed that the HDE layout is insufficient.
- 3: Action highlighting** is *not* helpful for recognizing asynchronous structures in the graph. However, this technique does help to see some of the graph structure. Allowing the user of the visualisation to assign a specified color to edges with a specific label helps significantly in model development.
- 4: Tapered edges** *are* considered as effective as standard arrows when analysing large graphs. The only disadvantage of this edge style is that the direction of an individual edge is hard to distinguish from a distance. However, for larger groups the general direction is easier to see when using tapered edges, compared to standard arrows.

5: Gradient edges *are* considered as effective as standard arrows when analysing dense graphs. Dense graphs become less cluttered by these edge shapes, and the direction of edges becomes easier to read. However, the opinions about the readability were divided.

6: Dedicated label UI is *not* preferred over indicating edge labels next to the hovered edge. The distance between the edge and the label causes delays, which makes it harder to analyse the actions in a large section. While on-demand action labels are considered more effective than showing all edges, it is preferable to show the label next to the cursor.

7: Semantic coloring *does* help understanding the graph structure. It was considered useful for confirming expectations and analysing properties. A simplified coloring implementation could improve user experience for simple cases.

8: Attribute clustering *does* increase graph readability when the model contains asynchronous elements. In the situation presented in the survey, the participants agreed that collapsing irrelevant actions improves readability. Compared to clustering confluent states, this technique is preferred when the actions to be ignored model a behaviour external to the system itself.

9: Showing confluent groups of states *does* help to understand behavioural similarities between states. The participants indicated that indicating the transitions involved would improve the visualisation considerably. We have not performed experiments to measure the performance of the algorithm, but from experience we expect the running time to be of the same magnitude as the HDE layout algorithm.

10: Clustering confluent states *does* help to understand behavioural similarities between states. Given that this clustering has already received much attention in literature, it is no surprise that it is considered useful. However, the participants agreed that attribute clustering may be preferred in certain use cases. Especially for large graphs, this clustering is also easier to compute than confluence.

13 Future Work

We discuss some open questions that we did not answer in our research.

13.1 Graph comparison

We considered the problem to find a subgraph in each of the two compared graphs, such that these two subgraphs are isomorphic. The problem of finding these subgraph is known as the maximum common edge subgraph problem [1].

This problem is NP-complete to solve exactly, but there are special cases that are interesting for our application. Generating the maximum *connected* common edge subgraph of two deterministic graphs given one matching pair of nodes can be solved with a greedy, linear-time algorithm. We designed and implemented this algorithm to research its applicability for non-deterministic graphs. As we conducted further research into non-deterministic graph, we found that even an approximation is infeasible [1].

A more restricted problem is Subgraph Isomorphism [5]. Subgraph isomorphism is the problem to identify a subgraph in a graph A that is isomorphic to the entirety of graph B . This is also an NP-complete problem, and any algorithm capable of finding the maximum common edge subgraph is trivially capable of solving subgraph isomorphism.

We researched a bit-vector algorithm capable of solving subgraph isomorphism in reasonable time, which is effective enough when B is small. We attempted to further modify this algorithm to generate a maximum common edge subgraph, but this was not successful. The major optimisations of this algorithm relied on checking whether any node in B could no longer be matched to any node in A . This property is not valid for a maximum common edge subgraph algorithm.

An effective way of visualising the isomorphic subgraphs is to visualise both graphs, and cluster every pair of node in the isomorphism relation. Specifically, given an isomorphism R and graphs A and B , we cluster all nodes $a \in A$ and $b \in B$ for which holds $(a, b) \in R$, and all edges $a \xrightarrow{p} a' \in A$ and $b \xrightarrow{q} b' \in B$ if aRb , $a'Rb'$ and $p = q$. We designed an effective color scheme, where graph A is colored transparent orange, graph B transparent green, and the clustered nodes black. As the only feasible algorithm had few practical applications, we decided to not include this visualisation in the survey.

In conclusion, we found that graph comparison is not feasible for the graph size where we are interested in.

There may be a method that uses information about the state space itself to detect the systematic changes between the graphs. Using state-specific information may give the algorithm a search priority, such that only a fraction of the possibilities have to be searched. These heuristics would only apply to graphs with node-specific data, but may prove to be very efficient.

13.2 Visualising larger graphs

Our rendering procedure is not efficient enough to effectively visualise graphs of over 50 000 nodes. To increase this limit, techniques could be employed to only visualise small sections in isolation. As the generation of a graph of these sizes takes a significant amount of time, this would likely also require an on-demand generation of the state space. Doing so also allows a detailed exploration of infinite graphs, without sacrificing details on an abstraction.

Alternatively, a top-level clustering is applied to the graph, where each cluster could be opened in isolation. This may be helpful for smaller graphs as well, when the connectivity hinders the graph readability.

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A Tool

To test the techniques and our hypotheses in this research, we designed a tool that implements these techniques. This tool allows visualising a graph using the techniques discussed in this thesis. The tool is implemented in Java 8, and uses OpenGL 3.3 for its rendering procedure.

Using this tool, we can analyse how these techniques perform in combination with other techniques. We used this tool as basis for our survey, and to run experiments on the performance of various techniques.

Graph manipulation Nodes can be manually moved using the right mouse button, and be anchored in place using the left mouse button. Clicking with left while holding the right button is supported. Edges can not be manipulated.

Colors The initial state is indicated with a green border and a green fill. Deadlock states are indicated with a red border. Anchored nodes are filled grey.

Hovering graph elements When an edge is hovered, all edges with the same label as this edge will be colored blue. The label of the hovered element will be shown below the mouse pointer. Left-clicking an edge will toggle its corresponding button in the *Action labels* list, as we will discuss later.

When a node is hovered, all nodes that are confluent to this node will be colored blue.

Load mu-formula The tool also allows loading a property as a modal mu-formula, which applies a coloring on the graph. In short, any edge that makes the property unreachable is colored red. Any edge where the property becomes unavoidable is colored green. The small X button resets the colors set by this function.

This function *does* work in combination with clustering.

Sliders The sliders control the force-directed layout.

The **Simulation step size** gives a trade-off between convergence speed and stability. If any part of the graph starts vibrating, the simulation step size should be reduced until the vibration disappears.

Attraction controls the strength with which edges pull their connected nodes together.

Repulsion controls the strength with which all nodes repel each other.

Natural length applies a base distance modifier to the algorithm, which influences the scale of the graph.

Handle repulsion controls the strength on which edges repel each other. This repulsion only applies to edges connected to the same nodes, and is mostly effective to split overlapping edges. These four sliders may be set to you own preference for this survey.

The **Heuristic Effect** allows the introduction of an heuristic to the forces computation. A high value reduces the time of each iteration, but also makes the force calculation less accurate. This is hardly a problem for our application, and a value of 1.00 results in a sufficiently accurate stable situation. This value is set automatically for large graphs, and there is no need to change it manually.

Action labels This is an alphabetically sorted list of all action labels in the graph. When clicked on the name of the action, the action in the graph is colored according to the current color.

Each action has an **I** button, to Ignore / Internalize the action. This marks the action as internal, and activates clustering on confluence.

Each action has an **C** button, to Cluster / Collapse all edges of this action. When collapsing an edge, the two nodes it connects are combined into one node.

Edge representation can be set to standard arrows, tapered edges and gradient edges.

The **3D view** allows toggling between a 2D and 3D visualisation. The graph is always flattened in the direction of the camera.

Graph painting The tool allows you to paint any graph element one of the preset colors, as long as *Activate Painting* is enabled. The color of a single edge can be set by left-clicking, and reset by right-clicking. All colors can be reset using the small **X** button.

Always use layout of primary graph can be toggled on to make the force directed layout only affect the primary graph, rather than the graph that is currently visualized. Enabling this allows you to switch between the different visualisations without the graph changing its layout, but also results in less optimal clustering results.

B Survey answers

In this section we list the answers on the survey questions. The questions are summarized, see section 10 for the full survey questions.

Twilight 1: Which of the two robots does the transportation from conditioner to drill?

A: The 'LoadRobot' moves the process from the conditioner to the drill.

C: I can select different actions, and I can clearly see the direction of the arrows, which suggests a certain order. But I have no clue how these actions correspond to the question, so I cannot answer it.

D: The load robot does the transportation from conditioner to drill.

2: Do the drill and the conditioner run asynchronously with the robots?

A: It seems that the conditioner and drill modules do not operate asynchronously. All actions pertaining to the conditioning module are located in one of the blocks and for the drill module in the other block.

C: I can see some structure in the graph, that is probably related to the question. Some parts are 2-dimensional, and in some parts it looks 3-dimensional. Probably the 3-dimensional parts correspond to asynchronous behavior, but I am not sure of that. I find it hard to answer the question, since I don't know what the actions mean.

D: When not interacting with the robots, the conditioner and the drill operate asynchronously with the robots as can be seen from the two 3D confluence "boxes" (one direction load robot, one direction unload robot, one direction drill/conditioner).

3: Does the highlighting of action help finding the asynchronous sections of the model?

A: (8) Highlighting actions did help enormously with answering question 2. I would rate this feature at least an 8. Perhaps it is useful to draw highlighted edges on top of all other edges, but not states. Furthermore, the ability to choose different colors for different labels could be useful.

C: The highlighting is useful to locate actions, and find the order between them. But I would need clearer instructions or more explanation about the model to relate this to asynchronous

behavior.

D: (8) When highlighting actions causes rows of transitions to light up, it is easy to see that there are multiple things running in parallel (asynchronously). For question 2 this was very useful.

4: Does the approach of the labeling in this tool hinder your search?

A: (8) For these questions having the labels be invisible is much better, so again an 8.

C: (5) The fact that I can control the coloring of individual actions is useful. But since all of them get the same color it quickly gets useless. Perhaps I missed the possibility to choose different colors.

D: (6) It helps keeping the graph clean, but needing to look back and forth between graph and top right and needing to remember every action is also not ideal.

Leader 1: Does the initial layout show a grid structure?

A: There is some type of grid visible, but the nodes are quite close together and this makes it difficult to distinguish the transitions.

B: Yes, I can see a grid-like structure, where each axis contains the same sequence of actions.

C: It's clear that some areas are more dense, but it's hard to distinguish a grid structure.

D: There seems to be some grid structure, but as the graph is rather attenuated it is difficult to see how this grid is structured.

2: Does the new layout show the gridlike structure better?

A: After simulation stabilises it is clear that the behaviour is asynchronous and is in fact a gridlike structure. It also shows a cluster of states that are more tied together. The resulting graph is better than the initial layout.

B: It improves the grid-like structure, but obscures some of the inner transitions.

C: This does make it a little better, but still the grid is not very clear.

D: The stabilised graph shows the grid structure better than the initial graph. The stabilised graph is rounder (more club shaped), which makes it easier to see the dimensions of the grid. The initial graph was rather at (more feather shaped), which did show that there was more going on in the center than on the outsides, but it was difficult to see how "deep" the grid actually is compared to the stabilised graph.

3: Does the highlighting of action labels help understanding which parts of this model are asynchronous?

A: The hide action functionality does not seem to work and it was difficult to highlight transitions outgoing from a specific state. So it is difficult to distinguish what is going on in the cluster.

B: (8.5) it improves finding parallel actions sequences, although it is hard to see how many exactly.

C: (2) The highlighting helps somewhat to see more structure in the model. But I don't know how this helps to answer questions about asynchronicity.

D: (7) Highlighting of the labels does help showing that there is asynchronous behaviour as you can approximately get an intersection through the graph, but because there are more actors than dimensions it is not very clear how this asynchronous behaviour is structured.

4: Does this representation improve the readability of the graph?

A: With the gradient feature it is easier to see the outgoing transitions of these nodes and to

confirm that there are in fact three distinct outgoing transitions.

B: The sense of direction of the overall system greatly improved.

C: This option definitely helps to see more structure in the graph, so indeed it improves the readability.

D: The gradient option does make the graph less black but I don't really feel like it improves the readability of the graph (but it does not really make it worse either). It also does not make selected edge stand out more (or less), maybe being able to define different display options for selected edges would help here?

Alma 1: Are there edges that represent an `execute` action that can not be repeated?

A: The red transitions indicate that in the future no execute action can be performed. This means that if such a transition is an execute action itself then this transition cannot be repeated.

B: Uncertain what the question means; the edges marked yellow ending up in a red node?

C: I can see yellow execute actions ending in a red dot. This tells me that after doing this execute action, it will never be possible to do another execute again.

D: Yes, these are the transitions that are red (when unselected)

2: There are 4 small loops where `execute` action has become unreachable. What does this mean if the system ends up in these states?

A: The system can never exit such a loop. B: No execute actions can ever be performed again. Furthermore, the system is life-locked. C: I can't distinguish loops, but I see clusters of red dots. This may indicate that when you enter such a cluster, you will never leave it again. D: That in from these states the execute action will never be possible.

3: With which action are the loops of question 2 entered?

A: The actions `auth_not_ok` with MT1 or MT2 for the first argument and Cont1 for the second.

B: Action `auth_not_ok`, indicated in red

C: With an execute action.

D: `auth_not_ok`

4: Does the formula-based coloring help understanding the behaviour of this graph?

A: (8) The formula based coloring does help with understanding the behaviour. I would rate this feature an 8. Perhaps it would be useful to specify these predicates within the tool by selecting the desired action labels for example.

B: (7) It does help with figuring out how the property given is reflected in the system. The general meaning of the system is still unclear to me.

C: (8) Yes, it helps to confirm certain expectations visually.

D: I feel like it helps somewhat, but it might be difficult to use this accurately to help understand the graph. The coloured arrows were somewhat confusing for me at first as well. I feel like an option to not do this colouring of arrows would be useful, because it distracts away from the actual states on which the formula is true. Also, the properties these arrows describe can be described using the mu-calculus (but then on states of course). It would also be better in my opinion if the states on which the property holds stand out more; now this is barely visible.

5: Does the tapered edge shape improve the readability of the graph?

A: This display option seems to be better than arrows to visualise the structure of the graph. This option might have also be useful for question 4 of the leader protocol.

B: Yes, it made the life-locks very obvious.

C: The tapered edges clearly suggest a direction. So in that sense they can be helpful.
D: It seems to improve readability somewhat (as well as gradient here), but I think this is mostly due how narrow and stretched the arrowheads are, which makes it difficult to see them from a distance.

Minepump 1: Does the pump system start running as reaction of a low methane level or a high methane level?

A: The pump is started as a result of detecting a high level. After the 'highLevel' action the shortest path to the pump becoming active does not contain a 'lowLevel' action.

B: High level, this was not very clear still using the shortest path. I had to colour particular states to find this out.

C: I created a shortest path from a state in lowLevel that goes through highLevel and ends in pumpRunning. So that seems to be the order in which these events occur.

D: High methane level.

2: Does clustering on confluence improve the readability of the graph?

A: This does improve the readability of the graph and makes it much easier to answer question 1, which is still the same.

B: It improved readability by reduction of transitions, but the task was similarly difficult to perform.

C: The clustering is very useful, because it makes the graph smaller. And this makes it easier to perform the previous task.

D: High methane level. The clustering made it significantly easier to check this (although I might be somewhat biased since I knew the answer due to the first question).

Reflection 1: Would you prefer labels to be visible in the graph?

A: Showing the edge labels only for the highlighted transition is fine in my opinion. However, I think that it would be quite nice to show the edge label next to the cursor or next to the highlighted transition instead of on the right.

B: Especially for the questions in section 3.4 it would have been beneficial to have transition labels.

C: Edge labels in the graph can be useful, especially when I want to explore the neighborhood of a state. But the solution of the tool is also useful. Being able to assign colors to certain actions really helps to focus on selected parts of a system. But I definitely would like to assign different colors to different labels.

D: Both have pros and cons. Showing labels makes it more cluttered, but not showing labels forces you to look back and forth and to remember the actions. Maybe it would be a good idea to be able to make transition labels visible in the graph when the user specifies this (when the action is selected or when clicking on the transition). This would have been useful for question 1 of twilight when I was trying to understand the model since I needed to remember the actions when I was going through the sequences of load/unload actions. Also, not having labels on transitions in the graph makes it difficult to hover on transitions when zoomed out. I had multiple times when looking to the top right for the action name that the mouse just managed to slip off the transition and I had to realign my mouse again.

2: Do you have a strong preference for a specific edge shape?

A: I quite liked the tapered edge visualisation, because it allows you to see the structure of

the graph as well as the incoming and outgoing edges. The gradient visualisation is mostly useful for the outgoing transitions.

B: I think a combination of tapered and gradients works the best. The tapered shape given the most sense of direction, and the gradient helps decluttering places in the graph where a lot of transitions overlap.

C: I still like traditional edges with arrow heads, because I find them aesthetically pleasing. But I was surprised to see that tapered edges can help to enhance the structure of the graph, and they also work well to indicate the direction of the edges.

D: I think I slightly prefer the tapered style, although the arrow style could be improved by making the arrow heads stand out more.

3: Did you consider using a 2D visualisation for any of the above graphs?

A: For these graphs the 3D visualisation is much better than 2D.

B: I did not, most nodes for the given graphs have more than two outgoing transitions, for which 3D mode is beneficial.

C: The 3D layout was perfect for me, I never missed a 2D projection.

D: No. I feel like 3D is always better if the graph is not 2D in itself, which was the case for all models used.